

D7.4

Report on the Implementation of Programmable Corpora

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0. About this Deliverable

In addition to this report, this Deliverable D7.4 includes a fully functional showcase for Programmable Corpora: the Drama Corpora Platform "DraCor", which has been under construction since 2018 and was further developed within CLS INFRA.

The main access points to the different components of the DraCor system are:

- Code and Data on GitHub: <https://github.com/dracor-org>
- DraCor web-based front end: <https://dracor.org/>
- DraCor API: <https://dracor.org/doc/api>

Numerous scholars participate in the development of DraCor and in the curation of the corpora (the latter is not part of this Deliverable). For an overview, see <https://dracor.org/doc/credits>.

For the DraCor platform as a whole, these persons are responsible:

- Editor-in-chief: Frank Fischer (Freie Universität Berlin)
- Co-editors: Peer Trilcke (University of Potsdam), Julia Jennifer Beine (Ruhr University Bochum), Daniil Skorinkin (University of Potsdam)
- Technical lead: Carsten Milling (University of Potsdam)
- Technical co-leads: Ingo Börner (University of Potsdam), Mathias Göbel (University of Göttingen)
- Tools: Henny Slyuter-Gäthje (University of Potsdam)
- Art director: Mark Schwindt (Freie Universität Berlin)
- Workflows, Corpus Building: Luca Giovannini (University of Potsdam)

1. Publishable Summary

Deliverable D7.4 captures the final maturation of CLS INFRA's Work Package 7 (WP7): „Building the Ecosystem of and for Programmable Corpora”. Since the earlier conceptual reports, the team has stabilised the DraCor platform and extended the “programmable corpora” model into a standards-compliant, extensively documented service. Central is the DraCorAPI version 1.0, whose version-prefixed paths, harmonised entity names and machine-readable OpenAPI description give scholars a reliable, citable interface to more than twenty drama corpora from (mostly) European languages with almost 4.000 plays. An accompanying ODD schema and emerging ontology aims to make every feature traceable from TEI source to JSON response. To widen interoperability, DraCor now implements *Distributed Text Services* (DTS) endpoints. During the last project phase, WP 7 has also broadened the internal and external tool stack: Two DraCor specific internal tools were introduced: *EzDrama* streamlines TEI encoding via a lightweight markup that facilitates conversion to XML, and *Who-is?* semi-automates the identifications of characters and the editing of character lists, accelerating corpus onboarding and quality control. With the implementation of a ToolTab in the DraCor front end, we now enable the direct input of texts from DraCor to the external tools *Voyant Tools*, *CLARIN Language-Resource Switchboard*, and *Gephi Lite*. Together, these advances transform an experimental prototype into a sustainable European infrastructure for computational literary studies.

2. A Programmable Future for Computational Literary Research. The Story So Far

2.1 A Vision

In his seminal essay “A Programmable Web” (2013), open-access activist Aaron Swartz proposed a vision of the Web where applications are not isolated, self-contained tools, but parts of an interoperable, dynamic ecosystem – “a section of the programmable web” (Swartz 2022, 7). For Swartz, the key to realizing such a web was the *natural growth* of APIs: open, machine-readable interfaces not appended as afterthoughts, but emerging organically from the data and services they expose. As the field of Computational Literary Studies (CLS) continues to develop and the need for concepts, services, and tools to improve the reproducibility, reusability and open circulation of literary data and software is growing, Swartz’s idea offers a kind of conceptual vision also for our discipline.

The concept of “Programmable Corpora”, introduced in 2019 by Fischer et al., implemented as a fully working prototype in the DraCor platform, and discussed in detail by Börner and Trilcke (2023), is a proposal to work towards the realization of Swartz’ vision. Within the horizon of CLS, “Programmable Corpora” serve a dual function: they are both epistemic objects and infrastructural nodes. Unlike traditional literary corpora – which are often prepared in the context of isolated projects, following divergent standards and often inaccessible beyond narrow use cases – “Programmable Corpora” are designed for interoperability, transparency, and computational interaction. Their “programmability” lies in the fact that they expose their structure and content through standardized APIs, enabling automated access to texts, metadata, and different types of derived data, such as network data or quantitative metrics. Instead of static or “dead-end” data files stashed on personal drives, these corpora are designed from the ground up for integrated, open-ended research. They encourage synergy among scholars, whether by seamlessly sharing texts, or by letting new microservices attach themselves to existing corpora. By fostering a specific style of infrastructural design, Programmable Corpora are expected to open up possibilities for collaborative, large-scale, and reproducible research in CLS.

Building on the preliminary work of the DraCor team, the CLS INFRA project work package 7: “Building the Ecosystem of and for Programmable Corpora” has worked both theoretically and practically on the elaboration and refinement of the concept of “Programmable Corpora“, on the one hand through extensive further development of the DraCor platform as a fully functional showcase, and on the other hand by transferring individual components to other corpora on a test basis or by connecting external components to DraCor. A design strategy rooted in distributed infrastructure was adopted. Rather than building a monolithic platform, the aim was to create an ecosystem of modular, interconnected services. This reflects a

commitment to embeddedness, flexibility, and sustainability-values essential to both technological design and scholarly practice.

2.2 Achievements of Deliverable D7.1: “On Programmable Corpora. Report and Prototype (DraCor)” and D7.3: “On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora”

In two reports, CLS INFRA work package 7 has conceptually elaborated and practically explored the vision outlined above. While report “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora. Report and Prototype (DraCor)” (Börner, Trilcke 2023) offered a general discussion of the concept of Programmable Corpora and its development within the DraCor prototype, and conducted initial experiments on the transfer of ideas and components to other applications and usage scenarios, report D7.3 “On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora. (Executable) Report and Prototypes for Reproducible Research” (Börner, Trilcke 2023) focused on the challenge of versioning “living corpora” as part of reproducible research.

From a general perspective, “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” laid out a conceptual model that integrates textual data, metadata, and associated micro-services into a distributed architecture. To transform these ideas into practice, the report introduced and documented “DraCor”, a prototype that reifies this concept in a concrete, multi-component environment. By homogeneously encoding theatre plays from multiple European languages in TEI, and then exposing these corpora through RESTful endpoints, “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” showed both seasoned and novice researchers how to run everything from basic queries for stage directions to advanced network analyses. Each component of the architecture – XML database, micro-services, APIs, a user-friendly interface – was explained in detail, illustrating how an ecosystem of openly licensed data and rigorously documented endpoints can accelerate scholarly inquiry.

Furthermore, “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” stands out for its commitment to the continued evolution of textual data. Unlike static corpora, DraCor corpora are designed to expand and adapt over time, reflecting the iterative nature of scholarly work. The report’s emphasis on agile methods, such as reflective prototyping, signaled that “living corpora” must remain open to transformation: new texts will be added; existing annotations may be revised; better metadata or updated standards will frequently require re-encoding. Recognizing these realities, “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” dedicated in-depth discussion to version control, reproducibility, and strategies to mitigate the challenges of data instability – pointing directly toward the deeper explorations in our report “D7.3 On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora”. In this sense, “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” did not merely deliver an operational prototype; it also set a research and development agenda for tackling complex questions of sustainability, traceability, and long-term scholarly engagement with evolving corpora.

In the following, we summarize the key achievements of past reports D7.1 and D7.3.

1. **Establishing the conceptual framework for “Programmable Corpora”:** One key conceptual contribution of D7.1 was to clarify what “Programmable Corpora” mean within the realm of CLS. Drawing on Aaron Swartz’s notion of the “Programmable Web,” the report reframed literary corpora as open, machine-actionable resources with documented APIs rather than static data silos. In addition, D7.1 introduced foundational concepts – such as APIs, microservices, and standardized metadata – that foster a research culture centered on agile, interconnected textual data.
2. **Delivering a fully functional prototype, the multilingual DraCor system:** Beyond theory, D7.1 introduced a working prototype: the multilingual Drama Corpora Platform (DraCor). Built around a RESTful architectural style, DraCor proved how a network-based ecosystem can be practically realized. The (still growing) platform features more than twenty corpora of around 4,000 theatre plays, stored in a central XML database and based on version control via GitHub. Such a fully operational system illustrated how the “Programmable Corpora” vision could effectively drive real-world CLS research. In 2023 and 2024 alone, we were able to identify 57 scientific publications that work with the DraCor platform.¹
 - 2.1. **Homogenizing literary corpora with TEI-based standards:** A central prerequisite for the functioning of DraCor is the homogenization of literary corpora using TEI/XML, ensuring consistent structure and metadata. D7.1 describes how TEI-markup enables cross-corpus comparisons by normalizing key features such as acts, scenes, and speaker identifiers.
 - 2.2. **Developing a research-driven, multi-component infrastructure:** Underpinning DraCor is a distributed infrastructure that connects data, APIs, and specialized micro-services for analysis (e.g. calculation of network measures) or Linked Open Data queries (SPARQL). The report D7.1 showed how this multi-component approach benefits researchers through modularity – each microservice can be developed or replaced independently without disrupting the entire system. Crucially, it also anticipates “living corpora”, integrating iterative updates and expansions throughout the infrastructure.
 - 2.3. **Offering open APIs:** Crucial for the “programmability” of DraCor, in D7.1 we documented all endpoints of the DraCor API that can be used to retrieve textual data, metadata, and derived data like network measures. Through the DraCor API we ensure that corpora are not just available but machine-accessible. Additionally, a SPARQL endpoint allows advanced linking to external knowledge bases, such as Wikidata. This API-first approach makes it easy to connect our corpora base with external scripts, web apps, or analytical pipelines to query and integrate theatre plays on a large scale.

¹ Cf. <https://dracor.org/doc/research>

3. **Demonstrating real-world use cases:** To bridge the gap between proof-of-concept and practical scholarship, D7.1 provided four concrete showcases. With these showcase, we demonstrated how novices and advanced users could:

- Download speaker co-occurrence networks for social network analysis in Gephi;
- Extract stage directions for NLP pipelines;
- Visualize performance locations via Linked Open Data;
- Automate multi-corpus queries to examine “Small World” metrics across thousands of plays.

These examples showed that DraCor’s “programmable” design directly empowers computational research in Literary Studies.

4. **Ensuring broad accessibility through a front end and CLS community engagement by open licences:** DraCor is connected to a user-friendly front end with a frontend that, among other things, makes the corpora browseable, offers some built-in visualisations, and grants one-click downloads of e.g. the TEI file of a play, network data, or text parts, such as stage directions or speaker text. D7.1 also commented on DraCor’s approach to community-engagement by hosting all corpora on GitHub under open licenses, encouraging collaborative expansions and corrections. By aligning technical openness with practical ease-of-use, DraCor tries to be approachable for a wide user base, from digital specialists to traditional literary scholars.

5. **Prototyping adaptability of DraCor components:** In D7.1, we further tested the adaptability of DraCor principles for other CLS resources, including:
- The Folger Shakespeare API, which we “swaggerized” according to the DraCor API,
 - POSTDATA’s poetry corpora, which we made browseable by re-using the DraCor front end.

These cross-project experiments showcased that the concept of “Programmable Corpora” can be extended well beyond drama analysis, providing another building block for our vision of a larger ecosystem of machine-actionable open-access textual data.

6. **Reflecting on versioning and implementing reproducibility workflows:** Finally, D7.1 laid the foundation for a deeper inquiry into how “living corpora” evolve over time. It highlighted that dynamic textual data complicates reproducibility and citation, since content or metadata regularly shift across updates. With this in mind, “D7.3 On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora” discussed and documented strategies to stabilize dynamic corpora (through commit referencing and containerization, e.g. with Docker) in greater technical detail.

3. Update on the Implementation of Programmable Corpora

3.1 Introduction

Since report D7.1, in which we provided the first in-depth explanation and contextualisation of the concept of “Programmable Corpora” and documented the DraCor prototype in detail, three tasks in particular have been addressed in work package 7 of the CLS INFRA project:

- Task 7.3 dealt with the “Technical stability of APIs for versioning and reproducibility”,
- Task 7.4 involved “Case studies on integrating existing apps into the ecosystem”,
- and in Task 7.5 we conducted research on “Non-consumptive reuse scenarios”.

At the same time, we worked continuously on optimising the DraCor prototype.

- First, in connection with Task 7.3, the further development of the DraCor API – as the centrepiece of the “Programmable Corpora” – and its consolidation in version 1.0 (published in April 2023) was important (see chapter 3.2).
- Second, we have expanded the documentation, such as setting up an ODD for the DraCor XML and documenting the API via the OpenAPI standard (see chapter 3.3).
- In the context of our explorations of a generic “Programmable Corpora” application, we have, third, taken up the generic standard DTS (Distributed Text Services) and implemented a corresponding DTS API (see chapter 3.4).
- Fourth, in connection with Task 7.4, we have created or further developed tools that can support the creation of DraCor corpora (see chapter 3.5).
- Also related to Task 7.4 are, fifth, our case studies on the connection of DraCor with other tools and services from the CLS and Digital Humanities ecosystem (see chapter 3.6).

We will report briefly on each of these in the following, with the implementation of DTS being discussed in more detail, including the technical aspects.

3.2 Improving the API Component of Programmable Corpora: DraCorAPI 1.0

The DraCor API is a specialized API built on top of the eXist-db database system², designed to facilitate digital drama analysis. It provides programmatic access to drama corpora³, enabling researchers to retrieve data related to dramatic texts, their metadata, and network metrics. The endpoints of the API are organized around two core entities – *corpora* and *plays* and offers domain-specific functionality tailored for drama analysis. For detailed documentation see our report “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora. Report and Prototype (DraCor)” (Börner, Trilcke 2023).

Overview of the DraCor API⁴

The DraCor API is implemented using RESTXQ⁵ in XQuery⁶, with endpoints defined in the `api.xqm` module. It supports multiple data formats, including JSON, CSV, XML, RDF+XML, TEI+XML, and plain text (TXT), making it versatile for various research and analytical needs. The API is documented using the OpenAPI Specification Format⁷, which provides a standardized, machine-readable description of its endpoints, supported HTTP methods, input/output schemas, and other details. This documentation is rendered interactively using Swagger UI, allowing users to explore and test the API directly in a browser.⁸

² Cf. <http://exist-db.org>. The version running on the production server at the time of writing of this report is 6.2.0. The version can be retrieved via the API endpoint `/api/v1/info`. The version number is output as DraCor API Feature `service_dependency_is_existdb_version`.

³ For an overview of the maintained corpora by the DraCor initiative see the “Corpus Registry” at <https://dracor.org/doc/corpora>.

⁴ For an in-depth explanation of the API see D7.1 On Programmable Corpora The information contained in this report is for the larger part still accurate – so, RTFR. Code references in D7.1 refer to the version 0.88.0. One can try to replace the commit hash `3215fde0c34cc51a51386728775cbb3c058ae06f` in the links to the code included in the appendix with `a8ec727c13b3a8d43da298b77ac989572c5c20a4` of version 1.0.2, but, depending on the changes, the line references to the code might still not be absolutely accurate then. The changes from version 0.88.0 to 1.0.0 and beyond are described in this chapter. The latest pre-release version as of this writing is version 1.1.0-beta.8. The version of the DraCor API deployed on the production server at the time of writing of this report is 1.0.2. Release: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.0.2> The version can be retrieved via the API endpoint `/api/v1/info`. The DraCor API version number is output as DraCor API Feature `service_version`.

⁵ Specification of RESTXQ:

<http://exquery.github.io/exquery/exquery-restxq-specification/restxq-1.0-specification.html>.

⁶ Cf. <https://www.w3.org/TR/xquery>

⁷ Specification see <https://swagger.io/specification>. The API specification of the DraCor API can be found in the `api.yaml` file on GitHub at

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/a8ec727c13b3a8d43da298b77ac989572c5c20a4/api.yaml>.

⁸ <https://dracor.org/doc/api>.

Core Entities: Corpora and Plays

- **Corpora:** The API allows users to retrieve information about drama corpora, including metadata such as titles, descriptions, licenses, and repository links. It also provides count-based metrics for corpora, such as the number of plays, characters, word tokens, and more.
- **Plays:** For individual plays within a corpus, the API provides detailed metadata, including titles, authors, genres, dates, sources, and network metrics. It also supports retrieving the full TEI-XML representation of a play.

Endpoint Structure

Endpoints in the DraCor API follow a consistent naming pattern, since API version 1.0.0⁹ typically structured as:

```
{base-url}/api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/{method}
```

For example:

- `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}`: Lists plays in a corpus.
- `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/tei`: Retrieves the TEI document of a play.
- `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics`: Provides network metrics for a play.

Data Formats and Content Negotiation

The API supports multiple data formats, with JSON being the most common. Some endpoints, such as those for network data, include the format in the URL (e.g., `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/networkdata/csv` or `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/networkdata/gexf` .

The format of the response can sometimes be controlled using the *Accept header* in the HTTP request, e.g. the endpoints `api/v1/id/{id}` and `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/spoken-text-by-character` return the data in a different format depending on the mimeType provided in the header of the request.

⁹ With DraCor API 1.0.0 the singular noun “play” was renamed to “plays” (see below). CLS INFRA Deliverable D7.1 offers a more extensive description of the API and its endpoints but follows the old naming convention.

Admin and Public Endpoints

- **Admin Endpoints:** These require authentication and are used for managing corpora (e.g., adding, updating, or deleting plays or corpora). They use standard HTTP methods like POST, PUT, and DELETE.
- **Public Endpoints:** These are accessible without authentication and are used to retrieve data for research and analysis. They primarily use the GET method.

Changes introduced with API version 1

The initial version of the DraCor API (version 0) was documented extensively in the CLS INFRA Deliverable “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” (Börner/Trilcke 2023). While much of the information still remains accurate, the API has since been revised based on insights gained from developing DraCor as a prototype for “Programmable Corpora”. These improvements culminated in the release of a stable version 1.0.0 in December 2023.¹⁰ The following section outlines the key changes introduced in this major update.

The transition from the “legacy” API 0.x to the stable release of the DraCor API introduced several significant breaking changes to improve consistency, clarity, and functionality.¹¹ The most notable changes are updates to the path structure.

Renaming `/play/` to `/plays/` in the URL of all endpoints

The path `/corpora/{corpusname}/play/...` has been changed to `/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/...`.¹² This change aims to better reflect the hierarchical relationship between corpora and their constituent plays.

Introducing a version prefix to all paths

A second, more general change to the path structure is the introduction of a version prefix (`/v1`) in all URL paths, ensuring that API consumers can clearly identify the version they are interacting with.

The “legacy” API can still be actively used on the production server under the `api/v0` path, e.g. <https://dracor.org/api/v0/info> returns the information on the available legacy API version, which is the last release 0.91.3.

The URLs without a version prefix used before the stable release are currently redirected to their `/v0` equivalents to support older tools still using the legacy API. This means that a request to <https://dracor.org/api/info> without the explicit version in the URL will still use the legacy API.

¹⁰ The release was announced with the following Blog Post: <https://weltliteratur.net/streamlining-the-dracor-api/>. Some of the information included there is outdated, e.g. on the “phasing out” of the API. Please refer to this report and the release notes (<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.0.0>) on the changes introduced with 1.0.0.

¹¹ See also the release notes for DraCor API 1.0.0 <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.0.0>.

¹² See changes to the codebase introduced with commit <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/7268c0331b3a5bf5f0d1e6c1366d93801cdc602e>.

Therefore, API calls included in the extensive documentation in D7.1 should still work as expected because calls to request urls without explicit version in the path will be redirected to the legacy API, e.g. <https://dracor.org/api/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> is redirected to <https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> and returns data on the play *Lessing: Emilia Galotti* using the old API version 0.91.3. The same result is achieved when explicitly including the `v0` in the path

<https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> from the beginning.

A request to <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> will fail (HTTP Error 400 Bad Request), as will

<https://dracor.org/api/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti> and

<https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti>, because the plural noun “plays” has only introduced to the path with version 1.

Generally, we advise to be explicit about which API version to use and include the path in the request URL to actively control which major version of the API to use.

Version 1 should be used from hence on. The legacy version 0 must not be used for new applications or research. It is only still around to support legacy applications that can not be updated to the new API version. We can not guarantee that the fallback behaviour will always work in the future, nor that we will be able to support multiple API versions in parallel.

In regards to the documentation in “D7.1 On Programmable Corpora” (Börner, Trilcke 2023) this affects all endpoints listed in

- Tables Tab. 02: Play Features (pp. 37–40),
- Tab. 03: Segment Features (p. 42), and
- Tab. 04: Character Features (pp. 43–44).

Renaming “cast” to “characters”

With version 1 the term “cast” has been renamed to “characters” in both URL paths and JSON properties to provide a more intuitive and accurate description of the data.¹³

Getting the character of a play in the legacy API v0 in the JSON format could be achieved with a request to <https://dracor.org/api/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti/cast> (now forwarded to <https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti/cast>). This data was also available in CSV format from the endpoint <https://dracor.org/api/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti/cast/csv>.

The now valid URL to get the characters of the play *Emilia Galotti* in the JSON format is <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti/characters> and the data as CSV is available under

<https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti/characters/csv>.

The legacy API included the characters of a play also in the response of the endpoint `v0/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}` as a JSON array included in the field with the key “cast”. For example, fetching the data of the play *Emilia Galotti* from

¹³ see GitHub issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/216>.

<https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> includes the characters as seen in the following (incomplete) example:

```
{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "cast" : [ {
    "id" : "der_prinz",
    "name" : "Der Prinz",
    "isGroup" : false,
    "sex" : "MALE"
  }, {
    "id" : "der_kammerdiener",
    "name" : "Der Kammerdiener",
    "isGroup" : false,
    "sex" : "MALE"
  }
  ... ]
}
```

The response data of the same play when requested from the version 1 endpoint as <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti> includes the characters in an array with the key “characters”:

```
{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "uri" :
  "https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "characters" : [ {
    "id" : "der_prinz",
    "name" : "Der Prinz",
    "isGroup" : false,
    "sex" : "MALE"
  }, {
    "id" : "der_kammerdiener",
    "name" : "Der Kammerdiener",
    "isGroup" : false,
    "sex" : "MALE"
  }
  ... ]
}
```

In regards to the documentation included in “D7.1 On Programmable Corpora” this affects Feature P44 `play_characters` as listed in the table “Tab. 02: Play Features” (p. 39):

No.	Feature	endpoint				
		<code>/corpora/{corpusname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/metrics</code>
P44	<code>play_characters</code>	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	<code>characters</code>	N.A.

Renaming property `dramas` to `plays`¹⁴

The plays included in a corpus are included in the response of the `/corpora/{corpusname}` endpoint. The “legacy” API returned it as an JSON array identified with the key `dramas`, e.g. in the plays included in the *German Shakespeare Corpus* <https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/gersh> are included as such (modified example):

```
{
  "title" : "German Shakespeare Drama Corpus",
  "repository" : "https://github.com/dracor-org/gershdracor",
  "name" : "gersh",
  "dramas" : [ {
    "id" : "gersh000008",
    "title" : "Wie es euch gefällt",
    ...
  }, {
    "id" : "gersh000037",
    "title" : "Was ihr wollt",
    ...
  } ... ],
  "acronym" : "GerShDraCor"
}
```

When requesting via the version 1 API from <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/gersh> the plays are included in an array with the key `plays`:

```
{
  "title" : "German Shakespeare Drama Corpus",
  "repository" : "https://github.com/dracor-org/gershdracor",
```

¹⁴ see changes to the codebase introduced with commit <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/84573f1c45f428f8a5ee88144401609fddc13079>.

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```

"name" : "gersh",
"plays" : [ {
  "id" : "gersh000008",
  "title" : "Wie es euch gefällt",
  ...
}, {
  "id" : "gersh000037",
  "title" : "Was ihr wollt",
  ...
} ... ],
"acronym" : "GerShDraCor"
}

```

This affects Feature C20 `corpus_play_objects` as listed in the “Table 01: Corpus Features” in D7.1 (p. 35):

No.	Feature	endpoint	
		<code>/corpora</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}</code>
...			
C20	<code>corpus_play_objects</code>	N.A.	<code>plays</code>

Harmonizing spelling of `year` properties

The spelling of year-related properties has been unified. Specifically, the properties `{print,premiere,written}Year` have been renamed to `year{Printed,Premiered,Written}`.¹⁵

In “D7.1 On Programmable Corpora” the inconsistencies in property naming can be seen in Table “Tab. 02: Play Features” (p. 38). The excerpt of the table below is unchanged, inconsistencies are highlighted:

No.	Feature	endpoint				
		<code>/corpora/{corpusname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics</code>
...						
P24	<code>play_year_written</code>	dramas.* writtenYear	*.yearWritten	yearWritten	yearWritten	N.A.
P25	<code>play_year_printed</code>	dramas.* printYear	*.yearPrinted	yearPrinted	yearPrinted	N.A.
P26	<code>play_year_premiered</code>	dramas.* premiereYear	*.yearPremier	yearPremiered	yearPremiered	N.A.

¹⁵ See pull request <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/pull/181> that introduces these changes to the codebase.

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			ed			
P27	play_year_normalized	dramas.*.yearNormalized	*.yearNormaliz ed	yearNormalized	yearNormalized	N.A.

The following rows of the table reflect the major change of version 1:

P24	play_year_written	plays.*.yearWritten	*.yearWritten	yearWritten	yearWritten	N.A.
P25	play_year_printed	plays.*.yearPrinted	*.yearPrinted	yearPrinted	yearPrinted	N.A.
P26	play_year_premiered	plays.*.yearPremiered	*.yearPremier ed	yearPremiered	yearPremiered	N.A.
P27	play_year_normalized	plays.*.yearNormalized	*.yearNormaliz ed	yearNormalized	yearNormalized	N.A.

Renaming of “genre” property

The property `genre` has been renamed to `normalizedGenre` in the response of the data returned by the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` endpoint.¹⁶

For example, a request to the legacy API at

<https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> returns the data in the modified example:

```
{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "genre" : "Tragedy",
  "libretto" : false,
  ...
}
```

The data requested from <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti> include the genre information as in the following modified example:

```
{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "normalizedGenre" : "Tragedy",
  "libretto" : false,
  ...
}
```

¹⁶ see issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/189>.

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}

This affects Feature P22 `play_genre_normalized` as listed in the table “Tab. 02: PlayFeatures” in D7.1 (p. 38):

No.	Feature	endpoint				
		/corpora/{corpusname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv	/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics
...						
P22	play_genre_normalized	N.A.	*.normalizedGenre	normalizedGenre	normalizedGenre	N.A.

Removing deprecated `author` property

The `author` property, which was deprecated in favor of the `authors` property, has been removed from the endpoints `/corpora/{corpusname}` and `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}`. This change eliminates outdated fields and streamlines the API's data model. The deprecation warning is not included anymore.¹⁷

Requesting data about a single play, e.g.

<https://dracor.org/api/v0/corpora/ger/play/lessing-emilia-galotti> includes the name of the author two times as can be seen in the modified example below:

```
{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "author" : {
    "name" : "Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim",
    "warning" : "The single author property is deprecated. Use the array
of 'authors' instead!"
  },
  "authors" : [ {
    "name" : "Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim",
    "fullname" : "Gotthold Ephraim Lessing",
    "shortname" : "Lessing",
    "refs" : [ {
      "ref" : "Q34628",
      "type" : "wikidata"
    }, {
      "ref" : "118572121",
```

¹⁷ See issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/187>.

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```

    "type" : "pnd"
  } ]
} ],
...
}

```

Requesting the data from the DraCor API 1.0 at <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti> includes the `authors` array only (modified example):

```

{
  "id" : "ger000088",
  "name" : "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  "corpus" : "ger",
  "title" : "Emilia Galotti",
  "authors" : [ {
    "name" : "Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim",
    "fullname" : "Gotthold Ephraim Lessing",
    "shortname" : "Lessing",
    "refs" : [ {
      "ref" : "Q34628",
      "type" : "wikidata"
    }, {
      "ref" : "118572121",
      "type" : "pnd"
    } ]
  } ],
  ...
}

```

In “D7.1 On Programmable Corpora” the variants of including the name(s) of the author(s) can be seen in Table “Tab. 02: Play Features” (p. 38). The excerpt of the table below is unchanged, the properties affected by the change are highlighted:

No.	Feature	endpoint				
		/corpora/{corpusname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv	/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics

P9	play_author_name	dramas.*.authors.*.name	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.name	N.A.
P10	play_author_name_en	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.nameEn	N.A.
P11	play_author_fullname	dramas.*.authors.*.fullname	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.fullname	N.A.
P12	play_author_fullname_en	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.fullname	N.A.

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					En	
P13	play_author_shortcode	dramas.*.authors.*.shortcode	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.shortcode	N.A.
P14	play_author_shortcode_en	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	authors.*.shortcodeEn	N.A.
P15	play_first_author_name	dramas.*.author.name	N.A.	N.A.	author.name	N.A.
P16	play_first_author_shortcode	N.A.	*.firstAuthor	firstAuthor	N.A.	N.A.
P17	play_first_author_deprecation_warning	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	author.warning	N.A.

The change introduced with API 1.0 removes the features P15 `play_first_author_name` and P17 `play_first_author_deprecation_warning` altogether.

Removing deprecated endpoints

With switching to major API 1.0 the deprecated endpoints

`/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata.csv`¹⁸ and

`/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/segmentation`¹⁹ have been eliminated.

Enhancements introduced to the API with version 1

Version 1 of the DraCor API also introduced major enhancements to improve functionality, usability, and integration capabilities.

Adding Schemas of responses to OpenAPI documentation

One of the key additions is the inclusion of schemas in the OpenAPI specification.²⁰ These schemas provide a clear and structured definition of the API's responses, ensuring better documentation and easier integration for developers. The schemas are also accessible from within the Swagger UI (see Fig. 01).

¹⁸ This endpoint is already declared deprecated in D7.1 On Programmable Corpora, see Footnote 82 on p. 41.

¹⁹ This endpoint is already declared deprecated in D7.1 On Programmable Corpora, see Footnote 83 on p. 41.

²⁰ see changes introduced to the codebase with commit

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/940d6ddb04ccf4700bca4da4ef8da10d5423a3>.

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200 Returns an object with play meta data

Media type

Controls **Accept** header.

Example Value | Schema

```

Play {
  wikidataId string nullable: true
  segments [SegmentItemInPlayMetadata {
    type string nullable: true
    speakers [string]
    number integer
    title string
  }]
  corpus string
  yearPremiered string nullable: true
  allInIndex number nullable: true minimum: 0 maximum: 1
  titleEn string
  authors [AuthorInPlayMetadata {
    refs [ExternalReferenceResourceId {
      type string
      ref string
    }]
    alsoKnownAs [string]
    fullnameEn string
    name string
    shortnameEn string
    nameEn string
    fullname string
    shortname string
  }]
  name string
  normalizedGenre string nullable: true
  subtitleEn string
  characters [CharacterInPlayMetadata {
    wikidataId string
    id string
  }]
}

```

Fig. 01: Schema of the response of the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` displayed in the Swagger UI.

Adding the `api/v1/wikidata/mixnmatch` endpoint

The `api/v1/wikidata/mixnmatch` endpoint, introduced in API 1.0, was designed by Frank Fischer and Viktor Illmer to support the integration of DraCor IDs (Feature P2 `play_id`) into Wikidata, facilitating the Mix'n'match import mechanism²¹. This endpoint returns data in CSV format, making it compatible with Wikidata's import tools and enabling seamless updates to the Mix'n'match catalog.

The purpose of this endpoint is to provide a structured way to import DraCor IDs into Wikidata, allowing dramatic works in the DraCor database to be matched with their corresponding Wikidata entries. This integration supports the alignment of DraCor data with Wikidata's extensive knowledge base, enabling rich cross-referencing and data enrichment.

The endpoint returns a CSV table with three columns:

- `id`: ID of the entry in the catalog – in case of DraCor it is the DraCor ID (Feature P2 `play_info`), a unique identifier for each play in the DraCor database.
- `name`: name of the entry in the catalog – in case of DraCor it is the main title of the play (Feature P5 `play_title`)²²
- `q`: The Wikidata ID (Q number) of the (manually) matched Wikidata entry (if available) – in case of DraCor this is the Wikidata ID (Feature P4 `play_wikidata_id`)

An example of the data returned by the endpoint is shown below:

```
id,name,q
als000001,"Der Pfingstmontag",Q77593548
als000002,"In's Ropfer's Apothek",Q83786534
als000003,"D'r Hoflieferant",Q90885236
```

This structured data can be used to import or update entries in a Mix'n'match catalog. The `id` column provides the unique DraCor ID for each work, the `name` column gives the title of the play, and the `q` column (if populated) indicates the corresponding Wikidata ID. If the `q` column is empty, it signals that the entry is unmatched and requires manual review or matching in Wikidata.

The introduction of the `api/v1/wikidata/mixnmatch` endpoint represents a significant step forward in integrating the DraCor database with Wikidata. In parallel to implementing the

²¹ See <https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Mix%27n%27match/Import>.

²² The function includes the main title only, see <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/4446437a4fbced7718f93d97a3ec2a76021d2332/modules/wikidata.xqm#L112>.

endpoint²³ a “DraCor Property” was proposed to Wikidata²⁴, which was accepted as property P12233²⁵ in December 2023.

DraCor IDs as defined as Wikidata Property are available, for example see <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q782653> (Fig. 02) As of April 2025 there are 1719 items on Wikidata that include a DraCor ID.

Fig. 02: DraCor property included in the entry of the play Emilia Galotti on Wikidata

Making “hidden” /author/{wikidataId} endpoint visible as `api/v1/wikidata/author/{wikidataId}`

Another significant change in Version 1 of the DraCor API involves the silent introduction of the previously “hidden” /author/{wikidataId} endpoint²⁶. While not explicitly mentioned in the release notes of 1.0.0, this endpoint has been part of the API since the legacy version but was not exposed in the OpenAPI Specification. Thus, it was unknown to most users. With the release of Version 1, this endpoint has been included in the specification and has become fully integrated into the user-facing API.

The `api/v1/author/{wikidataId}` endpoint provides information about authors from Wikidata. It retrieves data based on the author's Wikidata ID (Feature P19 `play_author_ref_external_id`) from the Wikidata SPARQL endpoint²⁷ and transforms this information to a JSON representation, allowing users to access structured metadata such as the author's biographical details (date and place of birth) and the URL to retrieve a profile picture.²⁸ For example, the endpoint could be queried to retrieve information about the german

²³ see commit

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/13b9365d41c67069c15c05f248af5f32ad0966b7> that implements the endpoint to the module `wikidata.xqm` as the xQuery function `wd:mixnmatch` at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/4446437a4fbced7718f93d97a3ec2a76021d2332/modules/wikidata.xqm#L101-L114>.

²⁴ see proposal at https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/DraCor_ID

²⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P12233>

²⁶ In “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” it is mentioned as “hidden” author endpoint when discussing the front-end, see p.60, esp. footnote 167.

²⁷ <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>. Set in the code at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/4446437a4fbced7718f93d97a3ec2a76021d2332/modules/wikidata.xqm#L13>.

²⁸ See the SPARQL Query included in the function `wd:get-author-info` in the module `wikidata.xqm` at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/4446437a4fbced7718f93d97a3ec2a76021d2332/modules/wikidata.xqm#L36-L99>.

author Gotthold Ephraim Lessing using the URL

<https://dracor.org/api/v1/wikidata/author/Q34628> which returns the following data:

```
{
  "birthDate" : "1729-01-22T00:00:00Z",
  "gender" : "male",
  "birthPlace" : "Kamenz",
  "deathPlace" : "Brunswick",
  "name" : "Gotthold Ephraim Lessing",
  "imageUrl" :
  "http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Special:FilePath/Gotthold%20Ephraim%20
  Lessing%20Kunstsammlung%20Uni%20Leipzig.jpg",
  "genderUri" : "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6581097",
  "deathDate" : "1781-02-15T00:00:00Z"
}
```

This endpoint was originally implemented to support the front-end functionality of the DraCor platform, where it was used to render author information when viewing a single play²⁹.

In the context of version 1.0.0, the original “hidden” endpoint `api/v0/author/{wikidataId}` has been restructured and is now accessible under the path `/api/v1/wikidata/author/{wikidataId}`. This change aligns with a broader effort to group endpoints that rely on or facilitate Wikidata integration under a common `/wikidata` path and also use the tag “wikidata” in the OpenAPI Specification for grouping (Fig. 03). This organizational change was proposed during the development of the `api/v1/wikidata/mixnmatch` endpoint, with the goal of making it clearer where the data originates and improving the overall structure of the API.³⁰

Fig. 03: Wikidata endpoints in the Swagger UI interface

Minor fixes and enhancements since version 1.0.0

Since the release of version 1.0.0, the DraCor API has undergone several minor fixes and enhancements to improve stability, performance, and usability. Since version 1.0.1³¹ the API running on the production server returns the status “stable” (API Feature

²⁹ For details on the front-end components that use the endpoint see D7.1. On Programmable Corpora, p. 60–61.

³⁰ see issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/192>.

³¹ <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.0.1>

`service_development_stage`) when requesting information about the API via the `/info` endpoint.³² Additionally, this release introduced the building of multi-platform Docker images³³ via GitHub actions on release and pushing them to Dockerhub.³⁴ This change is particularly significant for users wanting to run a local version of DraCor using Docker.³⁵ Multi-platform Docker images ensure that running a local DraCor system works smoothly on different architectures, such as newer Apple Mac computers with the ARM architecture. Having multi-platform images available boosts the performance of the infrastructural components by ensuring compatibility and optimization across various platforms.

The latest stable release, 1.0.2³⁶, was deployed to production on January 6, 2024, and remains the currently deployed version. This release introduced further refinements to the Docker setup. While these updates may seem incremental, they have ensured the API's reliability and performance over the past year, during which the team has been actively working on the upcoming 1.1.0 release. This next minor version will introduce new features and functionalities, with the latest pre-release version as of this writing being 1.1.0-beta.8.

Planned additions and changes to the API 1.1.0³⁷

DraCor API 1.1.0 will among other things add the following major enhancements:

- The Distributed Text Services (DTS) API is implemented. This adds four additional endpoints to the DraCor API `api/v1/dts`, `api/v1/dts/collection`, `api/v1/dts/navigation` and `api/v1/dts/document`. The DTS implementation is described in detail in section 3.4 in this report.

³² <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/4f8c49dc91ec3d59428a85cb7396bd9636e06ad2>

³³ On multi-platform builds with Docker see <https://docs.docker.com/build/building/multi-platform>.

³⁴ See commit

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/commit/711266fcb5a3876247922819b2139c2f4bac3c8a>. The DraCor API images are published on DockerHub at <https://hub.docker.com/r/dracor/api/tags>.

³⁵ See Chapter 4 “Dockerizing DraCor, for Example. On Versioning Programmable Corpora” in CLS INFRA deliverable “D7.3 On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora” (Börner, Trilcke 2024: 25–31), and the executable report at https://versioning-living-corpora.clsinfra.io/4_dockerizing_dracor.html.

³⁶ <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.0.2>

³⁷ The work on the 1.1.0 release is still ongoing. There have been some pre-releases that list some of the key enhancement, e.g. see release notes at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/v1.1.0-beta.8>. For the final added features see the release notes of version 1.1.0, a draft can be accessed at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/releases/tag/untagged-ef9a152d71f78ea9043a>.

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- The endpoint `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/txt`³⁸ is added. It allows retrieving the text of a whole play in the format `text/plain`. The transformation is realized by using XSLT³⁹.
- Following the insights from report D7.3 on how DraCor corpora are typically cited in research – often by the number of plays included or a specific date – we have introduced a more precise versioning indicator. The DraCor API now includes the Git commit hash of the version of a corpus stored in the database. This enhancement allows researchers to reproduce results based on the exact version of the corpus used, significantly improving transparency and reproducibility. The information will also be included in the front end (see Fig. 04)

Fig. 04: Truncated Commit Hash as link to GitHub in the card representing a corpus on the DraCor landing page.

³⁸ The endpoint is implemented with the function `api:play-txt` in the `api.xqm` module (<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L815-L836>). It relies on the utility function `dutil:extract-text` (<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L119-L130>) which can also be used to transform any TEI-XML element to plaintext.

³⁹ See `tei-to-txt.xsl` at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/tei-to-txt.xsl>

3.3 Improving Explainability through Documentation

In the rapidly evolving landscape of scholarly research and technological development, the importance of documentation cannot be overstated. Documentation serves as the backbone of any project, providing a comprehensive record of processes, decisions, and outcomes. It is particularly crucial in enhancing the explainability of complex systems, ensuring that stakeholders – from researchers and developers to end-users – can understand and trust the underlying mechanisms. This chapter explores how various forms of documentation, namely TEI ODD (“One Document Does it All”) and OpenAPI, contribute to improving explainability.

Explainability refers to the ability to describe the internal mechanics of a system in a way that is understandable to humans. In scientific and technological contexts, this is essential for validating results, ensuring reproducibility, and building trust. Documentation plays a pivotal role in achieving explainability by providing a clear and structured account of how a system works, why certain decisions were made, and what the expected outcomes are.

Documentation, while essential, presents significant challenges that can hinder its effectiveness. One of the primary difficulties is the need to create and maintain documentation concurrently with code development. This involves annotating functions, describing parameters, return formats, and the overall purpose of each component. While inline comments within the codebase serve as a form of documentation, they are typically invisible to end-users, such as researchers utilizing the system. This discrepancy highlights the need for a more accessible and user-friendly documentation approach.

Moreover, relying solely on code-level documentation is insufficient for end-users who rarely interact with the codebase directly. In systems like DraCor, the code remains the ultimate authority for understanding calculated metrics and system behaviors. However, making this internal documentation accessible to users poses a unique challenge. For instance, in reports for CLS INFRA produced by Work Package 7, references to specific lines of code in GitHub commits were included to provide transparency. While these references are stable, they become outdated as the codebase evolves, leading to misleading or incorrect information. This issue underscores the need for a documentation system that is both transparent and adaptable to changes in the codebase.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to develop methods that foster transparency by allowing direct code reviews while remaining flexible and adaptable. An incremental documentation approach, where documentation is continuously updated alongside code changes, can help mitigate the issues of outdated references. This approach ensures that users have access to the most current and accurate information, enhancing their understanding and trust in the system. By integrating documentation more closely with the development process, we can create a more robust and reliable documentation system that keeps pace with the evolving codebase.

Documenting a complex system like DraCor presents an additional layer of complexity due to the variety of documentation frameworks and formats in use. For instance, OpenAPI is employed to document the API, providing a standardized way to describe endpoints, request/response formats, and authentication methods. Concurrently, ODD (TEI “One

Document Does it All”) is utilized to document the TEI input data, offering a structured approach to detailing the data’s assumptions, mechanisms, and limitations. These disparate documentation systems, while each well-suited to their respective tasks, create a fragmented landscape that can be challenging to navigate.

The crux of the issue lies in the need to integrate these different documentation formats into a cohesive whole. Neither OpenAPI nor ODD can serve as a single, unified documentation system for DraCor. OpenAPI is not designed to document the intricacies of TEI input data, and there is no established best practice for using ODD to document APIs. Therefore, the solution must involve a distributed form of documentation, where each component is documented using the most appropriate framework and format. The key challenge then becomes developing the “glue” that links these disparate documentation elements, ensuring that users can seamlessly navigate between them and gain a comprehensive understanding of the system as a whole.

3.3.1 “Features”

To address the challenge of integrating diverse documentation systems, we introduce the concept of “features” as the unifying element that serves as the “glue” between various formats. These features represent specific types of values returned by the API, derived from extracting information from the underlying TEI-XML files and potentially applying various calculations or algorithms.

By defining these features explicitly, linking them to the code and using them as reference points in the various documentation formats (ODD for TEI-XML, OpenAPI for the API), we aim to create a clear and structured framework that makes the system’s inner workings more understandable to end-users.

Each feature is characterized by several key components: its type, the input data it relies on, namely the form of encoding information in TEI-XML, the extraction mechanisms employed (i.e. the XPath expression that is used to retrieve a value from the XML), and the algorithms implemented to generate the final value. By documenting these components comprehensively, we can provide users with a detailed understanding of how each feature is derived and what it represents. This approach not only enhances transparency but also ensures that the documentation remains closely aligned with the actual codebase, reducing the risk of discrepancies and outdated information.

By integrating feature definitions into our documentation, we create a direct link between the encoding scheme of the input data, the internal processes in the system and the API responses. This makes it easier for researchers and other users to trace the origins of the data they are working with, understand the calculations applied, and trust the results. Ultimately, this approach should foster a more transparent and reliable system, where the documentation serves as a living, evolving record of the system’s capabilities and behaviors.

The DraCor API defines a rich set of such features that describe the types of information or metrics that can be retrieved through its API endpoints. In our first report “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” these features are categorized into five main types: **corpus features**, **play features**, **segment features**, **character features**, and **network data features**. By

examining the key-value pairs in the API responses and considering various output formats, we have compiled comprehensive tables that not only list these features but also specify the endpoints and keys under which the data can be found.⁴⁰ The tables serve as a roadmap for users, enabling them to quickly identify and locate the specific data they need. They allow users to look up (the name of) features of interest and determine the appropriate endpoints to retrieve the desired information. Moreover, the tables facilitate a broader understanding of the API's data landscape, highlighting overlaps and discrepancies in the data returned by different endpoints. For instance, the transition from version 0.x to stable version 1.0.0 of the API involved correcting inconsistencies where the same information was returned under different keys.⁴¹ While these discrepancies have been addressed, the tables remain essential for users to navigate the API effectively and understand the distribution of features across endpoints.

The report “D7.1: On Programmable Corpora” not only categorizes and lists the features as tables but also includes detailed descriptions of the API endpoints. These descriptions provide users with a clear understanding of the purpose and functionality of each endpoint and include a link to the interactive OpenAPI documentation. Additionally, the report includes footnotes with links to the code of the respective XQuery modules and the specific XQuery functions associated with each endpoint. These references offer users a direct path to the underlying code, enabling them to delve deeper into the implementation details and gain a more thorough understanding of how the features are derived and processed.

As in science generally, transparency is paramount in the field of CLS. Researchers often build complex analyses on data derived from large collections of texts. The concept of Programmable Corpora emphasizes the use of APIs as a layer of stability and abstraction from the raw data. However, this approach requires a high level of transparency to ensure that researchers can trust and accurately interpret the data they retrieve.

When CLS researchers base their analyses on data retrieved via APIs, understanding how values are calculated is crucial for interpreting results accurately. For instance, a feature like P50 `play_network_density` represents the density of a co-presence network in a play.⁴² This value is obviously not included in the source data (the TEI-file representing a play) but is derived using network analysis algorithms. By defining this feature and linking it to the underlying functions in the code, researchers can trace how the value is computed (see also example below).

Such transparency ensures that researchers can reproduce analyses, validate findings, and understand the limitations of the data. This level of detail is essential for building trust in the

⁴⁰ See D7.1, p. 34, and the following sections “5.3.3.1 Information on a Corpus” (pp. 35–37), including Tab. 01: Corpus Features, “5.3.3.2 Information on a Play” (pp. 37–41), including “Tab. 02: Play Features”, section “5.3.3.3 Information on Key Constituents of a Play” (pp. 42.–47) including Tab. 03: Segment Features, Tab. 04: Character Features, section “5.3.3.4 Network Data” (pp.47–48); the table listing network features “Tab. 05: Network metrics provided by the DraCor Metrics Service” is on p.52–54.

⁴¹ see previous chapter 3.2 in the report, e.g. section “Harmonizing spelling of year properties” (`yearNormalized` vs. `normalizedYear`).

⁴² See D7.1. p.25, esp. footnote 42 on how co-presence networks are derived from the TEI data in DraCor.

API and the derived data, enabling more robust and reliable research outcomes. With DraCor’s documentation we aim to support this transparency.

While the current documentation approach provides a valuable starting point, it is not without its limitations. The prose descriptions of the system’s inner workings and the connections between the XQuery modules in the eXist-db XML database and the data returned by the API endpoints offer only a surface-level understanding. The tables, though useful, are limited in scope, listing only the names of features and the keys under which they appear in API responses. Crucially, they lack detailed information on how data is extracted and processed, and the links to the code can quickly become outdated as the codebase evolves. This makes it challenging for lay-users to fully comprehend the underlying mechanisms and for developers to maintain accurate documentation. Additionally, there is a notable gap in documenting how data must be encoded in the XML to ensure it is correctly returned by the API. This omission hinders users’ ability to effectively utilize the API and understand the requirements for data encoding. Addressing these shortcomings were and will be essential for creating a more robust and user-friendly documentation system.

A model of the data flow through the DraCor system

To understand what a single feature represents it is important to understand how the data flows through the system, from its initial encoding to its final presentation in the API response. In general, the data flow consist of the following steps:

- **TEI-XML Encoding:** The process begins with information encoded in TEI-XML format adhering to the DraCor schema. This structured data serves as the foundation for all subsequent operations.
- **Ingestion into eXist-DB:** The TEI-XML document is ingested into the eXist-DB system, where it is stored and managed.
- **Initial Information Extraction:** Upon ingestion, automated processes extract specific information from the TEI-XML file. For example, data representing a co-presence network is extracted and posted to an external service, the DraCor Metrics Service. On a conceptual level, there could be several of these extractor services being called. There are also some additional internal processes involved that create derived data, e.g. a XML-RDF representation.
- **External Processing:** The DraCor Metrics Service calculates network metrics using tools like NetworkX and returns a data structure serialized in XML that includes network metrics. This derived information is then stored back in the eXist-DB XML database alongside the original play.
- **User Request:** When a user requests data from an API endpoint defined in the `api.xqm` module, “extractor functions” in the `util.xqm` module are triggered. These xQuery functions use XPath expressions and/or xQuery FLWOR (“For, Let, Where, Order by, Return”) expressions to extract relevant bits of the XML.
- **Data Processing:** The extracted data may be further processed by XQuery functions, which perform additional computations or transformations as needed.

- **Response Assembly:** The final step involves assembling the processed data into a structured response, which is then returned to the user.

Fig 05: Overview of the data flow

Examples of how features manifest in the code

We can illustrate this with a simple and a more complex example: The first example shows how the English title of a play is extracted and included in the API response, the second, more complex example, shows the path from a single play to a single network metric.

First, we are interested in the English translation of the title of the play “Revizor” by Nikolaj Gogol’ from the Russian Drama Corpus. The play name is `gogol-revizor`, the DraCor ID `rus000054`. On the production server the play can be accessed at <https://dracor.org/rus/gogol-revizor>, or, using the ID resolver at <https://dracor.org/id/rus000054>.

P7 `play_title_en`

The front end does not display an english translation of the title of the play, but it is available via the API. The table “Tab. 02: Play Features” in D7.1 lists it as feature P7 `play_title_en`. The data is available either from the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}` endpoint or the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` endpoint⁴³:

No.	Feature	endpoint				
		<code>/corpora/{corpusname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}</code>	<code>/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics</code>
...						
P7	<code>play_title_en</code>	<code>dramas.*.titleEn</code>	N.A.	N.A.	<code>titleEn</code>	N.A.

The response object returned by a request to <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/rus/plays/gogol-revizor> indeed includes the English title “The Government Inspector”:

```
{
  "id" : "rus000054",
  "uri" : "https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/rus/plays/gogol-revizor",
  "name" : "gogol-revizor",
  "corpus" : "rus",
  "title" : "Ревизор",
  ...
  "originalSource" : "Н. В. Гоголь. Собрание сочинений в 9 т. Т. 4. М.: Русская книга, 1994.",
  "subtitleEn" : "A Comedy in Five Acts",
```

⁴³ Since API 1.0.0 the table in some regards is not accurate anymore. For instance the property “dramas” has been renamed to “plays” in case of the `corpora/{corpusname}` endpoint and the paths of the other endpoints now include the plural noun `plays` instead of the singular `play`, see section 3.2. “Changes introduced with API Version 1” in this report. This already demonstrates that the information in the table quickly becomes outdated, and, in its static form, is only of limited use.

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```
"titleEn" : "The Government Inspector"
}
```

This information is available because it has been explicitly encoded in the TEI-XML file in a very specific way⁴⁴:

```
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0" xml:id="rus000054"
xml:lang="rus">
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <titleStmt>
        <title type="main">Ревизор</title>
        <title type="main" xml:lang="eng">The Government
Inspector</title>
        <title type="sub">Комедия в пяти действиях</title>
        <title type="sub" xml:lang="eng">A Comedy in Five Acts</title>
      </titleStmt>
    <!-- ... -->
  </fileDesc>
</teiHeader>
<!-- ... -->
</TEI>
```

We demonstrated how to identify the correct endpoint to retrieve the information, observed how the information is included in the response object, and examined how the information is encoded in the source file. Now, we will delve into the internals of the API code⁴⁵ to identify the mechanisms relevant for extracting and producing this information.

The endpoint `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` implemented by the function `play_info`⁴⁶ in the `api.xqm` module:

```
(:~
: Get metadata for a single play
:
: @param $corpusname Corpus name
: @param $playname Play name
: @result JSON object with play meta data
:)
```

⁴⁴

<https://github.com/dracor-org/rusdracor/blob/6d5b1e5549731538a48684a456006384da206e9a/tei/gogol-revizor.xml#L9>

⁴⁵ For a more detailed explanation how an endpoint is implemented in xQuery using the RESTXQ framework, see chapter “5.3.1 Implementation” in D7.1, pp. 29–31.

⁴⁶

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L704-L726>

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```

declare
  %rest:GET
  %rest:path("/v1/corpora/{$corpusname}/plays/{$playname}")
  %rest:produces("application/json")
  %output:media-type("application/json")
  %output:method("json")
function api:play-info($corpusname, $playname) {
  let $info := dutil:get-play-info($corpusname, $playname)
  return
    if (count($info)) then
      $info
    else
      <rest:response>
        <http:response status="404"/>
      </rest:response>
};

```

The data to return is not generated by this function, but is retrieved by calling `dutil:get-play-info`⁴⁷ from the `util.xqm` module in the line:

```
let $info := dutil:get-play-info($corpusname, $playname)
```

The function `dutil:get-play-info` relies on yet another function, `dutil:get-titles`⁴⁸ to retrieve english titles: They get assigned to the variable `titlesEn` in the following code snippet⁴⁹ by passing the ISO language code `eng` as the parameter `lang`:

```
let $titlesEn := dutil:get-titles($tei, 'eng')
```

In `dutil:get-titles` the english translation of the main title is extracted from the source TEI file assigned to the variable `tei` using an `xPath` expression⁵⁰:

```
let $title :=
  $tei//tei:fileDesc/tei:titleStmnt
```

⁴⁷

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L956-L1132>

⁴⁸

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L866-L890>. There are actually two functions with the same name, that are only distinguishable by their function signature, i.e. the supported arguments.

⁴⁹

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L976>

⁵⁰

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L879-L882>

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```

/tei:title[@xml:lang = $lang and not(@type = 'sub')][1]
/normalize-space()

```

The function calling `dutil:get-titles` retrieves a xQuery map as a result. If an english title is available in this map, it is included in another map that acts as the basis of the response object finally by the API⁵¹:

```

if($titlesEn?main) then map:entry("titleEn", $titlesEn?main) else (),

```

From inspecting the code, we see that even in this simple example, it is necessary to traverse several function calls to arrive at the actual code that extracts the information. Fig. 06 visualizes the function calls as a sequence diagram:

Fig. 06: Sequence diagram of the function calls resulting in a value of feature `play_title_en` being returned

P58 `play_network_density`

We also discuss a slightly more complex example of a value that is not included in the source TEI file but is calculated based on structural information therein: the density of a network.

Network density refers to the proportion of actual connections (edges) in a network relative to the maximum possible number of such connections. In the context of a co-presence network within a play, network density provides insight into how interconnected the characters are. A higher density indicates a more tightly knit network, where characters frequently appear

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<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L1058>

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in the same scene and talk to each other, while a lower density suggests a more sparse network with fewer interactions.

Network properties are also displayed in the DraCor frontend.⁵² Fig. 07 shows the single play view of the play “The Government Inspector” by Gogol’ with the network density value highlighted.

Fig. 07: Network Density included in the Network Properties of the play Gogol’: Revizor

The value of the feature P58 `play_network_density` is available from several endpoints, as can be seen in the play feature table in D7.1.

⁵² See D7.1. section 5.6.3.1 Tab “Network” (pp. 61–62) for more details on the network view in the frontend.

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No.	Feature	endpoint				
		/corpora/{corpusname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata	/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv	/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}	/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics
...						
P58	play_network_density	N.A.	*.density	density	N.A.	density

1. `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata` is implemented with the xQuery function `api:corpus-meta-data`⁵³ in `api.xqm`;
2. `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata/csv` is implemented with the xQuery function `api:corpus-meta-data-csv-endpoint`⁵⁴ in `api.xqm`.
3. `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/metrics` is implemented by the xQuery function `api:play-metrics`⁵⁵ in `api.xqm`

The functions that implement the endpoints that return metadata on the whole corpus ultimately use the same utility function to retrieve the pre-calculated network metrics:

1. `api:corpus-meta-data` → `dutil:get-corpus-meta-data`
2. `api:corpus-meta-data-csv-endpoint` → `api:get-corpus-meta-data-csv`⁵⁶ → `dutil:get-corpus-meta-data`

The function `dutil:get-corpus-meta-data`⁵⁷ in the module `util.xqm` fetches all TEI files included in a single corpus and then iterates over these, fetching and/or calculating the individual data points. In case of the network metrics pre-calculated values generated upon the ingest of a file are used. The following line⁵⁸ retrieves this data using the xQuery `doc` function:

⁵³

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L603-L626>

⁵⁴

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L664-L678>

⁵⁵

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L761-L783>

⁵⁶

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L628-L646>

⁵⁷

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L562-L668>

⁵⁸

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/util.xqm#L594>

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```
let $metrics := doc($paths?files?metrics)/metrics
```

Whereas the path to the metrics file that is stored in the variable `$paths` is provided by the function `dutil:filepaths`⁵⁹ that expects the URL of location of the TEI file in the database supplied as its parameter.

The contents of the file `metrics.xml` stored in the database in `db/apps/dracor/corpora/rus/gogol-revizor` are included in the following code snippet:

```
<metrics updated="2025-04-23T09:15:25.985Z">
  <text>21327</text>
  <stage>2029</stage>
  <sp>19833</sp>
  <network>
    <averageDegree>14.838709677419354</averageDegree>
    <density>0.4946236559139785</density>
    <averageClustering>0.8233755852077903</averageClustering>
    <maxDegreeIds>gorodnichij</maxDegreeIds>
    <size>31</size>
    <maxDegree>26</maxDegree>
    <nodes>
      <node id="zhena_korobkina">
        <betweenness>0</betweenness>
        <degree>18</degree>
        <closeness>0.683739837398374</closeness>
        <eigenvector>0.21316888208185764</eigenvector>
        <weightedDegree>33</weightedDegree>
      </node>
      <!-- other characters represented by network nodes -->
    </nodes>
    <numConnectedComponents>2</numConnectedComponents>
    <numEdges>230</numEdges>
    <diameter>3</diameter>
    <averagePathLength>1.5195402298850575</averagePathLength>
  </network>
</metrics>
```

The network metrics are extracted in the function `dutil:get-corpus-meta-data` from this file using a FLWOR expression (similar to a loop) by transforming the XML data structure (see

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<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/uti.l.xqm#L16-L28>

listing below) into a xQuery map with the element name as key, e.g. `density` and the text node of the given element, e.g. `0.4946236559139785` as its value⁶⁰:

```
let $networkmetrics := map:merge(
  for $s in $metrics/network/*[not(name() = ("maxDegreeIds", "nodes"))]
  let $v := $s/text()
  return map:entry(
    $s/name(),
    if(xs:string(number($v)) != "NaN") then number($v) else $v
  )
)
```

3. `api:play-metrics` → `dutil:get-play-metrics`

A similar mechanism is used by the utility function `dutil:get-play-metrics`⁶¹ that is called from `api:play-metrics` – the function that implements the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/metrics` endpoint: The paths of the auxiliary files are here retrieved by the function `dutil:filepaths`⁶², which expects two parameters, `corpusname` and `playname`:

```
let $paths := dutil:filepaths($corpusname, $playname)
let $metrics := doc($paths?files?metrics)//metrics
```

and extracts the network metrics from the file with the following FLWOR expression, in which the element name is assigned to the variable `e` and the value of the element to `v` resulting in a xQuery map⁶³:

```
let $networkmetrics := map:merge(
  for $e in $metrics/network/*[not(name() = "nodes")]
  let $v := if($e/name() = "maxDegreeIds") then
    array {tokenize($e)}
  return map:entry(
    $e/name(),
    $v
  )
)
```

⁶⁰

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/utiL.xqm#L599-L606>

⁶¹

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/utiL.xqm#L1076-L1132>

⁶²

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/utiL.xqm#L30-L42>. This function calls another function with the signature `dutil:filepaths($corpusname as xs:string, $playname as xs:string, $filename as xs:string)`.

⁶³

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/utiL.xqm#L1119-L1128>

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```

else
  $e/text()
return map:entry(
  $e/name(),
  if(xs:string(number($v)) != "NaN") then number($v) else $v
)
)

```

The resulting map is then merged with other metrics resulting in the response object that is returned by the endpoint.

We have demonstrated so far that the value for the feature `play_network_density`, which is included in the responses of three endpoints, is ultimately retrieved from a pre-generated XML file stored in the database. To fully understand how these values are calculated upon data ingest of a corpus, yet another deep dive into the code is necessary.

Loading of a corpus is triggered by two requests to the API: First, the corpus needs to be registered by posting some metadata resembling information in the `corpus.xml` file to the endpoint `api/v1/corpora` endpoint, e.g.

```

{
  "name": "rus",
  "title": "Russian Drama Corpus",
  "repository": "https://github.com/dracor-org/rusdracor"
}

```

This endpoint is implemented by the function `api:corpora-post-json` in the `api.xqm` module.⁶⁴ The function calls an utility function, `dutil:create-corpus`⁶⁵ which creates an XML data structure, basically a `corpus.xml` file, to be sent to the function `dutil:create-corpus` expecting the XML and a corpus name as its parameters.⁶⁶ When a corpus has been successfully registered, the loading process is triggered by posting an object with a single key `load` and the boolean value `true` to the `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}` endpoint. This functionality is provided by the function

⁶⁴

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L337-L391>. There is also a possibility to directly POST a `corpus.xml` file as payload. This is implemented with the function `api:corpora-post-tei`, <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L256-L335>.

⁶⁵

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/uti.xqm#L1308-L1344>

⁶⁶

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/uti.xqm#L1346-L1363>

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`api:post-corpus`⁶⁷ in `api.xqm`. This schedules the job⁶⁸ to load the corpus from a GitHub with the xQuery `load-corpus.xq`⁶⁹, calling the function `load:load-corpus`⁷⁰ from module `load.xqm`.

When a play is added to the database the trigger function `trigger:after-create-document`⁷¹ in the module `trigger.xqm` calls⁷² the function `metrics:update`⁷³ in the module `metrics.xqm`. This function causes the metrics to be generated by calling `metrics:calculate`⁷⁴ – the function that creates the contents of the `metrics.xml` file. The network metrics are embedded into the XML by the function `metrics:get-network-metrics`⁷⁵ which based on the extracted segment data and the distinct speakers retrieves the metrics from the *DraCor Metrics Service*.⁷⁶

The DraCor Metrics Service is a Python-based microservice that calculates network metrics for the DraCor system. It exposes a single API endpoint, `/metrics`, which accepts POST requests containing structural data extracted from TEI files in JSON format.

⁶⁷

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L462-L549>

⁶⁸

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/api.xqm#L529-L532>

⁶⁹

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/jobs/load-corpus.xq>

⁷⁰

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/load.xqm#L72-L132>

⁷¹

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/trigger.xqm#L14-L23>

⁷²

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/trigger.xqm#L18>

⁷³

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/metrics.xqm#L170-L184>

⁷⁴

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/metrics.xqm#L151-L168>

⁷⁵

<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/72e35d2b3f702a10a61a9cf00c672d54d42a629f/modules/metrics.xqm#L81-L149>

⁷⁶ For a more detailed description of the Metrics Service and the payload it expects, see D7.1. On Programmable Corpora, pp. 51–53. Since version 1.4.0 the package *fastapi* is used instead of *hug* to implement the API of the service. The latest version of the metrics service at the time of writing (version 1.5.0) uses *networkX* version 3.4.2.

The service is implemented using the *hug* package and relies on the *networkx* library for network analysis. The density of the network is calculated⁷⁷ with the package’s function *density*⁷⁸.

While the examples provided demonstrate how a “close reading” of the code can shed light on the extraction and calculation of feature values included in API responses, this approach presents significant challenges. The complexity of the code, combined with the functional programming style inherent in xQuery, makes manual review a time-consuming and demanding task. Functions often call other functions in a nested manner, creating a labyrinthine structure that requires meticulous tracing to understand the flow of data and the logic behind calculations.

This complexity poses a substantial barrier for the average researcher using DraCor. Manually reviewing code demands not only a considerable amount of time but also a high level of expertise in both the programming language and the specific codebase. Such expertise cannot be expected of most researchers, who may lack the technical background or experience needed to navigate the intricacies of the code.

3.3.2 DraCor API Ontology

To address the challenges of explainability and enhance the documentation of the DraCor API, we introduce the DraCor API Ontology⁷⁹. This ontology provides a machine-readable, semantically enriched way to document the features returned by the API, ensuring a more structured and accessible understanding of the data.

This version (1.0.0) of the DraCor API Ontology formally defines the features identified in the report D7.1 “On Programmable Corpora”. It incorporates the changes made for version 1 of the DraCor API, ensuring that the ontology is up-to-date with API version 1.0.0-beta.1.

The DraCor API Ontology relies on the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM)⁸⁰, a comprehensive and extensible top-level ontology designed for the cultural heritage domain. CIDOC-CRM provides a formal structure for describing the implicit and explicit concepts and relationships used in cultural heritage documentation, ensuring semantic interoperability and a shared understanding across different systems and datasets. By leveraging CIDOC-CRM, the DraCor API Ontology benefits from a well-established framework that facilitates the integration and interpretation of data, enhancing the semantic richness and consistency of the API responses.

The primary purpose of our ontology is to add semantics to the responses specific to the DraCor API. Conceptually, the instances of the classes defined in the ontology should be understood as very specific data structures which are “information objects”. They are all subclasses of the top level class “API Response Data”, which is formally a subclass of `D1`

⁷⁷ See <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-metrics/blob/main/app/main.py#L76>.

⁷⁸ See the NetworkX documentation of *density*:

<https://networkx.org/documentation/stable/reference/generated/networkx.classes.function.density.html#networkx.classes.function.density>.

⁷⁹ https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/blob/main/v1/dracor_api_ontology.ttl

⁸⁰ https://cidoc-crm.org/sites/default/files/cidoc_crm_version_7.1.3.pdf

Digital Object of the CIDOC-CRM extension CRMDig⁸¹. D1 Digital Object, in turn, is a subclass of E73 Information Object from CIDOC-CRM. For example, an instance of the class “Author” represents information about an author structured in a very specific way. According to CIDOC-CRM, this would be an instance of `crm:E73 Information Object`, not an instance of the class `crm:E39 Actor` or its more specific subclass `crm:E21 Person`.

The ontology defines several annotation properties that allow attaching additional information to the features included. They also serve the purpose of enabling the reconnection of the ontology to its initial source (the report D7.1), as well as to other documentation formats, such as the OpenAPI specification and the DraCor codebase. Below is an overview of these annotation properties:

- **Feature ID** (`:feature_id`): The ID of the feature as listed in the report "On Programmable Corpora" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7664964>). This ID corresponds to the 'No.' column in Tables 01, 02, 03, and 04 of the report.
- **Feature Name** (`:feature_name`): The slug used to identify the feature in the report "On Programmable Corpora." This slug corresponds to the 'Feature' column in Tables 01, 02, 03, and 04.
- **xPath** (`:xpath`): The XPath expression that extracts (or can be used to extract) the information from a DraCor TEI file starting at the document root. This expression is for reference and may not be the exact construct used in the XQuery-based implementation of the API in the eXist-db.
- **API Module** (`:extractor_in_api_module`): The name of the XQuery module in the DraCor API eXist-DB application that contains the function(s) used to extract the information from the source document.
- **Extractor in API Function** (`:extractor_in_api_function`): The name of the XQuery function that contains the code used to extract the information from the source document or derived data structure in case of the metrics.
- **Code Reference** (`:code_ref`): A reference to the code lines that contain the relevant code for extracting the information. These are normally GitHub links identifying single lines or ranges of lines in the code. Unfortunately, these are hard to keep updated as the codebase changes.
- **Operation ID** (`:operation_id`): The operation ID ('operationId') in the OpenAPI Specification Document of the DraCor API.
- **Field Key** (`:field_key`): The key of the field in the JSON response object. While aimed at consistency across endpoints, there might be several keys, so this information should be handled with care and not used for automatic processing.

Features representing single data values are generally modeled as `owl:DataTypeProperties`. However, some features in the API responses are expressed by

⁸¹ CRMDig. An Extension of CIDOC-CRM to support provenance metadata. v3.2.1.
<https://cidoc-crm.org/crmdig>

nested data structures, such as JSON objects or arrays of objects. These features are transformed into `owl:ObjectProperties`, following the pattern `contains_{X}_data`.

The following code example shows how the feature P7 `play_title_en` is defined in the ontology. Common properties from the RDFS scheme are used to assign a label (`rdfs:label`) and a description (`rdfs:comment`). The domain and the range of the property are defined. It can be used to assign textual content (`rdfs:Literal`) to an entity representing data about a play. The specialized annotation properties listed above are used to attach additional information relevant to describing the feature in more detail:

```

:play_title_en
  a owl:DatatypeProperty, rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:domain :Play ;
  rdfs:range rdfs:Literal;
  rdfs:label "play title english"@en ;
  rdfs:comment "English translation of the original main title of the
play. Extracts the text of the element <tei:title> with 'eng' as the
attribute's @xml:lang value."@en ;
  :feature_id "P7" ;
  :extractor_in_api_module "util.xqm" ;
  :extractor_in_api_function "dutil:get-titles" ;
  :code_ref
<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/665ea3f07c3f0ab83566440436
691ed73957b263/modules/util.xqm#L865-L868> ,
<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/665ea3f07c3f0ab83566440436
691ed73957b263/modules/util.xqm#L961> ;
  :xpath
"/tei:TEI/tei:teiHeader/tei:fileDesc[1]/tei:titleStmt/tei:title[not(@type
= 'sub') and @xml:lang = 'eng' and ./ancestor::tei:TEI/@xml:lang !=
'eng']/normalize-space()" ;
  :operation_id "list-corpus-content", "play-info" ;
  :feature_name "play_title_en" .

```

The DraCor API Ontology provides a structured and machine-interpretable version of the feature definitions that were previously only available in tabular format. By defining each API feature in RDF, the ontology enables automated processing and integration, making it easier for systems to understand and utilize the features without manual interpretation. This machine-readable format enhances interoperability and ensures consistency across different applications and platforms that interact with the DraCor API.

One of the key advantages of the ontology is its potential use in JSON-LD contexts⁸². By incorporating the ontology's properties into JSON-LD contexts, the API responses can include embedded documentation, making them self-descriptive and more informative. We have already

⁸²On the JSON-LD context see <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/#the-context>. The DraCor API currently does not return JSON LD. We identified a simple mechanism to provide this format, which will be implemented in the future. See the following issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/302>.

applied this approach by reusing the ontology for the DraCor-specific JSON-LD contexts included in the extension MetadataObjects included in the responses of the DTS Collection and Navigation endpoints (see chapter 3.4).

Although the DraCor API Ontology is already well-defined, it is currently not fully integrated into the DraCor system. This lack of integration presents several challenges that need to be addressed to realize the ontology's full potential and improve DraCor's integration into the Linked Data Cloud. For instance, the classes and properties defined in the ontology are not dereferencable via the DraCor system, limiting their machine readability and use by RDF-aware clients.

To overcome this challenge, several enhancements can be considered. One approach is to either extend the capabilities of the `api/v1/id/{id}` endpoint and adapt the ontologies base URI starting with <https://dracor.org/id/{ontology-specific-slug}>. This would allow to use the already existing resolver endpoint to at least provide RDF data on the classes and properties. This can be achieved by depositing the DraCor ontology in the Apache Jena Fuseki Triple Store component of DraCor⁸³. The resolver could then translate a request to the endpoint into a SPARQL query with the URI of the concept or property in the subject position (variable `?uri` in the SPARQL Query below) and returning all statements about this entity:

```
SELECT * WHERE {
  ?uri ?p ?o .
}
```

This means the system could return RDF in different serializations (e.g., RDF/XML, Turtle, JSON-LD) based on the request, making the ontology more flexible and accessible. Furthermore, providing a human-readable view of a class or property would significantly enhance the user experience, making it easier for researchers and developers to understand and utilize the ontology. A similar approach to updating the existing resolver endpoint could be to more clearly separate the ontology from the other linked data accessible via the `api/v1/id/{id}` resolver by adding an “Ontology resolver” endpoint that would work the same way as described above (e.g., with URIs https://dracor.org/ontology/play_name).

While these enhancements require additional work, they have the potential to yield better results by improving the integration, accessibility, and usability of the DraCor API Ontology. By addressing these challenges, the ontology can become a more valuable and integral part of the DraCor system, facilitating better semantic interoperability and documentation.

3.3.3 Enhancing OpenAPI

To further improve the usability and interoperability of the DraCor API, we have made significant enhancements to the OpenAPI documentation. Initially, we added response schemas for all endpoints defined in the OpenAPI specification with the 1.0.0 release of the API. This

⁸³ See an overview of DraCor components in D7.1: On Programmable Corpora, p. 21-22.

improvement has another benefit: It allows for the automatic generation of a core module for the API wrapper PyDraCor⁸⁴, we are calling “PyDraCor Core”⁸⁵. This package is then reused in the PyDraCor library to increase the efficiency of API calls. This automation not only streamlines the development process because it is possible to always keep the core wrapper in sync with the developments of the API, it also ensures consistency and accuracy in API interactions.

A further enhancement to the OpenAPI documentation will involve reusing the feature names or URIs defined in the ontology to annotate the schemas included.⁸⁶ OpenAPI provides two key properties (“JSON Schema Annotation Keywords”)⁸⁷ to further describe a property in the response: `title` and `description`.

Currently, a schema definition in the OpenAPI documentation of DraCor does not use these additional properties to annotate a schema property (although, the “links” to the ontology – the local ids – are included as human-readable comments):

```
components:
  schemas:
    PlayInCorpus:
      # see api:corpus-index
      type: object
      properties:
        id:
          # ontology: #play_id
          type: string
        titleEn:
          # ontology: #play_title_en
          type: string
```

This property could be annotated using `title` and `description` as follows. The information would be included in the interactive Swagger documentation as seen in Fig. 08:

```
titleEn:
  # ontology: #play_title_en
  title: English Subtitle
  description: English translation of the original main title of
the play. Extracts the text of the element <tei:title> with 'eng' as the
attribute's @xml:lang value.
  type: string
```

⁸⁴ See CLS INFRA Deliverable D7.2 API Libraries for R and Python for the Programmable Corpora Prototype “DraCor”: “rdracor” and “pydracor”.

⁸⁵ <https://github.com/dracor-org/pydracor/tree/automatic-api/openapi-generated-wrapper>

⁸⁶ See corresponding issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/issues/305>.

⁸⁷ See “Schema Object” in <https://swagger.io/specification/> and <https://json-schema.org/understanding-json-schema/reference/annotations>.

Fig. 08: Schema including title and description of the property titleEn displayed in the Swagger UI

The OpenAPI standard can to be extended by custom properties.

“Extensions (also referred to as *specification extensions* or *vendor extensions*) are custom properties that start with *x-*, such as *x-logo*. These are used to add extra information or functionality that the OpenAPI standard doesn’t include by default.”⁸⁸

In the case of DraCor an extension for adding the links to the ontology and, possibly, the ODD can thus be added relatively easily by introducing custom properties, e.g. *x-ontology* and *x-odd*. When added to the DraCor OpenAPI Specification the custom properties also show up in the Swagger Documentation (Fig. 09):

⁸⁸ https://swagger.io/docs/specification/v3_0/openapi-extensions/

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```

components:
  schemas:
    PlayInCorpus:
      # see api:corpus-index
      type: object
      properties:
        id:
          # ontology: #play_id
          type: string
        titleEn:
          # ontology: #play_title_en
          title: English Subtitle
          description: English translation of the original main title of the play.
          Extracts the text of the element <tei:title> with 'eng' as the attribute's @xml:lang
          value.
          type: string
          x-uri: https://dracor.org/ontology/dracor-api/v1/play_title_en
          x-odd: https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_title_en

```

By annotating the OpenAPI schema with feature names or URIs from the ontology, we create a more interconnected and semantically rich documentation framework. This approach not only improves the clarity and usability of the API but also ensures that the documentation remains consistent and aligned with the underlying ontology. As a result, developers and researchers can more easily understand and interact with the DraCor API, leading to more effective and efficient use of the system.


```

Corpus v {
  name* > [...]
  title* > [...]
  acronym* > [...]
  description > [...]
  commit > [...]
  repository > [...]
  licence > [...]
  licenceUrl > [...]
  plays
    v {PlayInCorpus v {
      id* > [...]
      uri* > [...]
      name* > [...]
      title* > [...]
      subtitle > [...]
      titleEn English Subtitle v string
        title: English Subtitle
        x-uri: "https://dracor.org/ontology/dracor-
          api/v1/play_title_en"
        x-odd: "https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_title_en"
        English translation of the original main title of the play.
        Extracts the text of the element <tei:title> with 'eng' as the
        attribute's @xml:lang value.
      subtitleEN > [...]
    }
  }
}

```

Fig. 09: Additional custom properties documenting the property `titleEn` displayed in the Swagger UI

3.3.4 Enhancing ODD

The Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) standard is defined using the schema meta-language ODD (One Document Does It All). An ODD is a TEI document that contains both machine-readable models of the elements and attributes used in a document as well as schema fragments. It also includes human-readable documentation texts, such as editorial guidelines, code examples, and references to the TEI Guidelines. This comprehensive approach ensures that the ODD serves as a centralized and coherent reference for encoding practices and customizations within a project.

From its inception, DraCor has defined its encoding model using the ODD (One Document Does It All) framework, which provides a comprehensive and flexible approach to defining TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) schemas.⁸⁹

Initially, our strategy was to produce a highly restrictive schema that allowed only the elements and attributes supported by the API. This approach aimed to ensure consistency and compatibility with the API's capabilities, but it sometimes met resistance from groups that wanted to integrate their corpora into DraCor and needed to support additional TEI elements or attribute values in their systems.

Until last year (2024), our schema generation process explicitly included only the elements supported by the API in the TEI module definitions (`<moduleRef>`) within the central schema specification (`<schemaSpec>`). We also removed unsupported attributes on the level of the individual included elements (`<elementSpec>`) and restricted the allowed attribute values by setting the `@type` attribute of value lists `<valList>` of attributes to `"closed"`. The resulting relaxNG schema was highly restrictive, allowing only the elements and attributes explicitly included and defined in the ODD. This rigidity, while ensuring high compatibility with the API, limited the flexibility and extensibility of the encoding model.

Recognizing the need for greater flexibility, we revised our strategy for generating the schema.⁹⁰ We shifted towards a more inclusive approach, incorporating all elements from the modules included in the TEI Drama Customization (tei-drama)⁹¹. Additionally, we have now adopted the use of attribute value lists `<valList type="semi">`, which include proposed values (those supported by the API) but do not restrict users to these values alone. This semi-open approach allows users to use other attribute values as needed, providing greater flexibility while still guiding them towards the values supported by the API.

These changes allow for a broader range of TEI elements and attributes to be used, providing more flexibility for users who need to encode additional information in their documents. This relaxed approach to the DraCor schema has both advantages and challenges. On the one hand, it provides users with the flexibility to encode a wide range of information

⁸⁹ See code in GitHub Repository dracor-schema <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-schema>. The ODD is <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-schema/blob/main/dracor.odd>.

⁹⁰ See Pull-Request <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-schema/pull/82> and also issue <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-schema/issues/66> with some contextual information and the discussion of the process.

⁹¹ https://tei-c.org/release/xml/tei/custom/odd/tei_drama.odd, also <https://tei-c.org/guidelines/customization/#section-1>.

without being overly restricted from the outset. This inclusivity supports the integration of diverse corpora into the DraCor system. On the other hand, it can lead to situations where a document that validates against the DraCor schema contains information that cannot be processed by the API. This discrepancy can cause confusion for editors and users of the system who expect certain information to be output by the API simply because it is included in the TEI source document.

To address this potential confusion, it is crucial to clearly communicate the capabilities and limitations of the API to users. The now extended Encoding Guidelines also included in the reworked DraCor ODD emphasize that while the schema allows for a broad range of TEI elements and attribute values, the API may not support all of them. Providing guidelines and examples of what is supported can help users understand how to encode their documents in a way that aligns with the API's capabilities. A preview of the new Encoding Guidelines (the HTML rendering of the ODD) is available at <https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd>.

While we cannot delve into all the changes included in the DraCor ODD—as there are many and the process is still ongoing—we will focus here on our approach to integrating the “features” into the ODD. This integration is a crucial step in enhancing the documentation of the DraCor system, ensuring that users have a clear and structured reference for understanding what features are supported by the API and how they therefore need to be encoded in the source documents.

We began by taking the DraCor Ontology in its RDF/XML serialization. This format provided a structured and machine-readable representation of the features, and utilized XSLT (Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations) to transform the owl:DatatypeProperties into TEI-XML encoded descriptions. An example of a feature description is included in the code snippet below:

```
<div xml:id="play_title_en">
  <head>Play English Title</head>
  <p>
    Feature <idno type="feature-no">P7</idno>
    <idno type="feature-id">play_title_en</idno>:
    English translation of the original main title of the play.
  </p>
  <p>
    The respective function extracts the text of the element
    <gi>title</gi> with <val>eng</val> as the attribute's
    <att>xml:lang</att> value.
  </p>
</div>
```

The information included in the TEI representation of a feature is not as rich as in the ontology which provides a means for defining annotation properties that can hold additional, relevant information in a machine-readable way. Still, there is some information carried over to the TEI while the main benefit is having an `xml:id` that allows for referencing the feature in the ODD,

e.g. in the Encoding Guidelines. This also results in a link to the feature description in the HTML rendering of the ODD: https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_title_en

In the example above, the `play_title_en` feature is described in TEI-XML format. The `<head>` element provides a human-readable title for the feature, while the `<p>` elements offer detailed descriptions and explanations. The `<idno>` elements are used to record the identifiers, i.e. the name of the feature (`feature-id`) and the feature number (`feature-no`) included in the original feature tables in our report D7.1.

We previously mentioned the challenge that encoders might face in understanding how to encode information in their TEI-XML files to ensure that the API outputs the desired data. To address this issue, we have introduced a solution called “feature checks” into the DraCor Schema, leveraging Schematron rules.

Schematron is a rule-based validation language for XML that complements traditional schema languages like RelaxNG. Unlike this schema language, which focuses on the structure and data types of XML documents, Schematron allows for the definition of complex rules that can validate the content and relationships within the document. This makes it particularly useful for enforcing encoding practices and ensuring that specific features are correctly implemented.

The following code snippet shows such a feature check as included in the ODD as a `<constraintSpec>`.⁹² Fig 10 shows how it is rendered in the HTML output:

```
<!-- P5      play_title -->
      <constraintSpec ident="play_title" scheme="schematron"
type="api_feature_check" corresp="#play_title">
      <desc>
        Feature-Check:
        <name type="api_feature">
          <ref target="#play_title">P5 play_title</ref>
        </name>
      </desc>
      <constraint>
        <sch:rule context="/" role="information"
see="https://dracor.org/doc/odd#play_title">
          <sch:let name="play_title"

value="/tei:TEI/tei:teiHeader/tei:fileDesc/tei:titleStmt/tei:title[not(@type =
'sub') and not(@xml:lang or ./ancestor::tei:TEI/@xml:lang =
@xml:lang)]/normalize-space()"/>
          <sch:report
test="/tei:TEI/tei:teiHeader/tei:fileDesc/tei:titleStmt/tei:title[not(@type =
'sub') and not(@xml:lang or ./ancestor::tei:TEI/@xml:lang = @xml:lang)]">
            Supported API feature: play_title [value:
            <sch:value-of select="$play_title"/>]
          </sch:report>
        </sch:rule>
```

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<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-schema/blob/e1c304422434722d20809eff751ad48d1b37768e/dracor.odd#L6221-L6239>

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```

</constraint>
</constraintSpec>

```

Schematron Feature-Check: P6 play_subtitle

```

<sch:rule context="/" role="information"
see="https://dracor.org/doc/odd#play_subtitle">
<sch:let name="play_subtitle"
value="/tei:TEI/tei:teiHeader/tei:fileDesc/tei:titleStmt/tei:title[@type
='sub' and not(@xml:lang or ./ancestor::tei:TEI/@xml:lang = @xml:lang)]/normalize-space()"/>
<sch:report test="tei:TEI/tei:teiHeader/tei:fileDesc/tei:titleStmt/tei:title[@type='sub']"> Supported API feature: play_subtitle [value:
<sch:value-of select="$play_subtitle"/>]
</sch:report>
</sch:rule>

```

Fig. 10: <ConstraintSpec> implementing Feature Check P6 play_subtitle displayed as HTML

By integrating Schematron rules into the DraCor Schema, we can define precise checks that look for certain encodings within the TEI-XML files.⁹³ These rules can then provide immediate feedback to encoders, indicating whether a particular feature is supported and correctly encoded. For example, in the Oxygen XML Editor, these Schematron rules can highlight sections of the document and offer guidance on how to encode information to ensure compatibility with the API. For example, in Fig. 11 a user of the Oxygen XML Editor is informed that the encoded play supports the feature play_title.

Fig. 11: Feature Check as displayed in the Oxygen XML Editor

By implementing feature checks using Schematron, we aim to make the encoding process more intuitive and less error-prone. This approach helps encoders understand the specific requirements for each feature and ensures that their TEI-XML files are correctly encoded to work seamlessly with the DraCor API.

⁹³ See https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#index.xml-body.1_div.5_div.6 for a HTML rendering of the already implemented Schematron checks.

3.4 Implementing the Standard API Specification DTS in DraCor for Enhanced Data Access⁹⁴

3.4.1 Introduction

The implementation of the “Distributed Text Services” (DTS) Specification (Cayless et al. 2024) within the DraCor platform, on which we report in the following, represents an important development in enhancing the generic capabilities of DraCor and the concept of “Programmable Corpora”, making it more suitable for a broader range of applications in Computational Literary Studies. While on the one side the DraCor API serves as the backbone of the platform, enabling researchers to interact with dramatic texts in programmatic ways, it is on the other side crucial to recognize that the DraCor API is a custom solution tailored specifically to the needs and structure of DraCor. In the end, it is not a standardized API that can be universally applied across different projects or initiatives. This custom API, while beneficial for DraCor's specific use cases, limits its reusability for other purposes without significant adaptation.

This report demonstrates the feasibility of facilitating specific endpoints of the DraCor API to send data to external tools such as the CLARIN Switchboard, Voyant Tools, and Gephi light for further processing (see chapter 3.6). However, it is important to note that this capability must be explicitly foreseen and integrated into the API as well as into the front end. Currently, there is no use case where an external, generic software client can directly interact with the DraCor API without additional adaptation, either on the side of the client or on the side of DraCor.

As the ecosystem of “Programmable Corpora” continues to expand, both in general and within the specific context of DraCor, there is a growing need for more generic and widely applicable APIs. These APIs should ideally cover the document-driven functions that are currently handled by the DraCor API, but in a manner that allows for broader adoption and integration across diverse projects, and possibly, in generic client software.

In work package 7 of the CLS INFRA project, which aims to further develop and enhance DraCor, the search for such generic APIs has been a key focus. The goal was to identify and implement standards that can complement parts of the DraCor API, thereby increasing interoperability and fostering a more cohesive ecosystem for text corpora access in the field of CLS and beyond.

There are some API specifications that have been created to enhance the interoperability and sharing of collections of text data. One early example is the “Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting” (OAI-PMH). It is a protocol designed to facilitate the interoperability and exchange of metadata between digital repositories. The primary function of OAI-PMH is to allow metadata aggregator services to harvest data from individual data providers. The protocol defines a standardized way to request and retrieve metadata. It

⁹⁴ This chapter is available as an executable Jupyter notebook in a slightly adapted form as “Distributed Text Services (DTS) in DraCor” at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks/blob/main/dts/dts.ipynb>.

supports incremental harvesting, allowing service providers to efficiently update their metadata collections without needing to download the entire dataset repeatedly. In regards to data representation, OAI-PMH is quite flexible, because it can be used with various metadata formats. Dublin Core is commonly used as a default.

While OAI-PMH is highly effective for general metadata exchange, it was not specifically designed for handling text collections. Its generic nature means it lacks certain features desirable for text-specific applications, such as the ability to retrieve individual texts, or even individual portions of it without downloading the entire collection. Despite these limitations, OAI-PMH remains a foundational protocol in the realm of digital libraries and repositories, promoting open access and interoperability. For instance, it is the protocol that powers CLARIN’s aggregator services, most notably the “Virtual Language Observatory” (VLO, <https://vlo.clarin.eu>)⁹⁵

A specification that was tailored specifically to foster the exchange of text was the “Canonical Text Services” (CTS) protocol⁹⁶ developed by the Homer Multitext Project at Harvard’s Center for Hellenic Studies (Blackwell and Smith 2019). CTS makes it possible to address individual passages of, especially, canonical texts by using a custom identifier scheme (CTS URNs). While there are some implementations apart from the Homer Multitext Project, e.g. the Coptic SCRIPTORIUM (Almas and Schroeder 2016), CTS was never widely adopted outside the field of Digital Classics and, as of today, can be considered deprecated.

A more recent development in the realm of text exchange is the “TextAPI” specification⁹⁷, developed at the State and University Library of Göttingen. TextAPI is designed to facilitate the interoperability and sharing of textual data, much like how the IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) enables the sharing of image data. While the TextAPI is an interesting candidate for becoming a more widely adopted standard in accessing texts and we at DraCor closely monitor its development and adoption in the field, this chapter will delve into the already finished implementation of the DTS Specification as a step towards a more interoperable API for DraCor. We explore how DTS aligns with the existing DraCor API and investigate the potential benefits it brings to the platform. We also evaluate its use as a more general API for “Programmable Corpora” in general.

3.4.2 On our DraCor DTS implementation

We implemented the API endpoints defined in the DTS Specification to the codebase of the DraCor API eXist-DB application in the module `dts.xqm`⁹⁸. At the time of writing the final stable

⁹⁵ Cf. “Providing Data to the VLO”, <https://vlo.clarin.eu/help>.

⁹⁶ https://cite-architecture.github.io/ctsumn_spec

⁹⁷ <https://textapi.sub.uni-goettingen.de>

⁹⁸ The version of the DraCor API that includes the xQuery module that is discussed in this chapter is 1.1.0-beta.6, see <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/f2a9c451b2080f9d2bcbd54a221a38da9c086c3d/modules/dts.xqm>.

version 1 of the DTS has not been released. We implemented the DTS Specification of a version that was tagged “unstable”, the version that followed “1-alpha”.⁹⁹

The DraCor API now provides the four additional endpoints specified by DTS. The following schematic (Fig. 12)¹⁰⁰ is an overview of the endpoints defined by DTS, their general function and the returned data format.

Fig. 12: Schema representing the resource model underlying each DTS model, the type of data it exposes, as well as the required format of expression (Almas et al. 2023, adapted)

In the following we discuss these endpoints in more detail. Based on the explanation of the quite simple to understand “Entrypoint” endpoint we offer some information on the general principles and technical solutions used in DTS (e.g. URI Templates and JSON-LD as return format to

⁹⁹ See a snapshot of the page in the Internet Archive at <https://web.archive.org/web/20250317100350/https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/versions/unstable/>.

¹⁰⁰ The original figure, "Schema representing the resource model underlying each DTS model, the type of data it exposes, as well as the required format of expression," in Almas et. al (2023) is based on an older version of the DTS specification. Since then, the names of the endpoints have been updated to singular forms and the concept of a "passage" seems to be replaced with the concept of a "Citable Unit", see also GitHub issue <https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications/issues/249> that removes the "passage" property.

support Linked Data). The other, more complex endpoints “Collection”, “Navigation”, and “Document” are explained further below by providing practical examples of how they can be used.

3.4.3 The “Entrypoint” endpoint and some general DTS design principles

api/v1/dts (DraCor DTS Entrypoint)

This is the main entry point for accessing the DTS API within DraCor. It provides an overview of the other available DTS endpoints and can serve as a starting point for navigating the API's capabilities. Users can retrieve metadata about the DTS implementation, such as the version, and, in theory, this endpoint should allow a DTS client to self configure by evaluating the provided links to the other endpoints.

Below is the response of a request to the DraCor DTS Entrypoint at <https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts>:

```
{
  "@context":
  "https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/context/1-alpha1.js
  on",
  "@id": "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts",
  "@type": "EntryPoint",
  "dtsVersion": "unstable",
  "collection": "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection{?id,nav}",
  "document":
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document{?resource,ref,start,end,mediaTy
  pe}",
  "navigation":
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation{?resource,ref,start,end,down,
  tree}"
}
```

The property `dtsVersion` specifies the version of the specification that is implemented, the values of the properties `collection`, `navigation` and `document` contain so-called “URI Templates”.

URI Templates

The DTS Specification uses URI Templates as defined in RFC 6570¹⁰¹: “A URI Template is a compact sequence of characters for describing a range of *Uniform Resource Identifiers* through variable expansion.” These patterns allow a client to construct URIs dynamically by expanding variables marked in curly brackets `{}`.

¹⁰¹ <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc6570>; see also <https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/versions/unstable/#about-uri-templates>

For example, the response of the DraCor DTS Entrypoint contains the URI Template of the Collection endpoint

```
https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection{?id,nav}.
```

From this it is possible to deduce that there are two supported query parameters `id` and `nav`. When values for these two variables are provided, a client should expand the URI Template containing a question mark `?` followed by a sequence of parameter names separated by comma `,` into a valid URI by substituting the first parameter with the sequence `?` followed by the variable name, equals sign `=` and the the value of the first variable. For every other variable name in the comma separated list contained in the curly brackets, a client should substitute the variable name with an ampersand `&` followed by the variable name, an equals sign `=` and the value of the given variable.

In the case of the above included URI Template and with the supplied values `ger000001` as the first variable, the identifier `id` of a single resource, and `parents` as the value of the second parameter `nav`, a client should construct the following URI:

```
https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=ger000001&nav=parents.
```

JSON-LD

As with the other endpoints that return metadata, the response of the Entrypoint is in the “JSON-LD” format. Using JSON-LD as a return format in DTS offers several significant benefits, particularly in terms of data interoperability and usability. One of the primary advantages is the embedded documentation it provides. The context within a JSON-LD document allows for the definition of terms, enabling users and systems to easily look up and understand the meaning of each term. This self-describing nature enhances the clarity and usability of the data, making it more accessible to developers and researchers alike.

In the “JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data”¹⁰², the key-value pairs within the returned JSON object are called *properties*. Each key represents a property name, and the corresponding value is the property value. The first three properties included in the response (see above) are defined by the JSON-LD specification:

`@context`: defines the context for interpreting the JSON-LD data. The value is a URI pointing to a document that maps the terms used in the data to their respective URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers).¹⁰³

¹⁰² <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld>

¹⁰³ For most of the properties the developers of the DTS specification provide these mappings under the URL <https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/context/1-alpha1.json>, but in the case of the “Entrypoint” the properties `dtsVersion`, `collection`, `document` and `navigation` are not defined.

`@id`: This default JSON-LD property provides a unique identifier for the resource being described.

`@type`: This standard property specifies the type of the resource returned. In the case of the response of the Endpoint endpoint the described resource is of the class `EntryPoint` as defined by the URI <https://w3id.org/dts/api#EntryPoint>. Because JSON-LD is a serialization of RDF the function of this property is the same as in Turtle stating that a thing is an instance of a class: `ex:Thing rdf:type ex:Class`.

DTS and Linked Data

JSON-LD is a Linked Data format, which – apart from providing “embedded” documentation of the responses – brings further advantages. By leveraging Linked Data principles, JSON-LD facilitates the integration of data from diverse sources, allowing for richer and more interconnected datasets. This interconnectivity enables more sophisticated data queries and analyses, as it allows for the seamless linking of related information across different systems and platforms. Furthermore, the use of Linked Data promotes data reuse and sharing, fostering a more collaborative and interconnected data ecosystem. Overall, JSON-LD’s ability to provide context and link data makes it an ideal choice for enhancing the utility and interoperability of data returned by DTS.

The current implementation of DTS as Linked Data still faces some challenges. One significant issue is the incomplete JSON-LD context, which lacks a comprehensive ontology. This incompleteness can lead to ambiguities and inconsistencies in data interpretation, as the defined classes and properties do not fully align with the latest DTS specifications. The schematic (Fig. 13) shows the classes of objects and the interconnecting object properties defined in the specification (data properties are skipped here). The classes and object properties in red are not included in the available DTS JSON-LD context files `1-alpha1.json`¹⁰⁴ and `1.0.0draft-2.json`¹⁰⁵ published in the official DTS repository on GitHub at <https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications>.

¹⁰⁴

<https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications/blob/cd287d0b1d18ef98904b42c5fd8c2eba1208c9ce/context/1-alpha1.json>

¹⁰⁵

<https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications/blob/cd287d0b1d18ef98904b42c5fd8c2eba1208c9ce/context/1.0.0draft-2.json>

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Fig. 13: Overview of Classes and Object Properties of DTS

As a solution to this problem we proposed a reworked JSON-LD context that includes all terms used in the current DTS specification.¹⁰⁶ The terms in this context reference properties and classes of an OWL Ontology¹⁰⁷.

Initially, when designing the DTS specification the authors choose “Hydra” (Hypermedia-Driven Web APIs) (Lanthaler and Gütl 2013) as the API design approach “for its more stringent support of hyper-media API best practices, and especially the use of JSONLD for expression of linked data” (Almas et al. 2023). Hydra is a framework designed to facilitate the development of web APIs that are driven by hypermedia principles – the use of hyperlinks and other interactive elements within digital media to create a networked and interconnected information environment. These principles are central to the design of the World Wide Web and are based on the idea that content should be interlinked, allowing users to navigate seamlessly between related pieces of information. In the context of web APIs, hypermedia principles are embodied in the concept of “Hypermedia as the Engine of Application State” (HATEOAS) (Fielding 2000), where the API responses include hyperlinks that guide clients on how to

¹⁰⁶ See pull request on GitHub: <https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications/pull/273>

¹⁰⁷ See <https://github.com/ingoboerner/dts-specifications/blob/0d71f4b8a890da94dae56e1886c4b26cf8aad34/context/dts-ontology.ttl>

interact with the API, dynamically discovering available actions and resources without needing prior knowledge of the API structure. This approach promotes a more adaptable and scalable API design, making it easier to evolve and integrate with other systems. While offering a robust framework for building hypermedia-driven web APIs, Hydra is not as widely adopted as some other API design paradigms like REST or GraphQL. API documentation frameworks like OpenAPI (see chapter 3.3) are far more widely used.

In its current version, DTS can at most be considered Hydra-inspired. This inspiration is evident in features such as providing the DTS “EntryPoint” endpoint as the main starting point, which allows clients to dynamically discover the other three endpoints. Additionally, DTS includes URI Templates in its responses, enabling clients to dynamically construct request URLs to retrieve more information about a resource. These elements reflect a Hydra-like approach to enhancing API discoverability and interaction, even if the full Hydra framework is not completely implemented.

In regards to the Linked Data approach inherited from Hydra, DTS re-uses only three terms from the “Hydra Core Vocabulary”¹⁰⁸ `hydra:title`, `hydra:description` and `hydra:member`. The first two, `title` and `description`, are Datatype properties (in the sense of OWL) and are used to attach plain Literals to instances. They are derived from the very general properties `rdfs:label` in the case of `hydra:title` and `rdfs:comment` in the case of `hydra:description`.

However, re-using the `hydra:member` term from the Hydra vocabulary imposes certain restrictions on the Distributed Text Services (DTS) Specification. The `hydra:member` property is defined as a property of the `hydra:Collection` class. The property definition lists `hydra:Collection` as the `rdfs:domain`, meaning that any instance using `hydra:member` must also be considered an instance of `hydra:Collection`. This constraint affects DTS because it uses `hydra:member` not only for collections of texts returned by the Collection endpoint, but also for another purpose, such as listing “citable units”, i.e. in the case of DraCor referenceable acts, scenes, speeches and stage directions in the response of the Navigation endpoint.

Ideally, this should be considered when designing the ontology for DTS, but the information on the “future” of Hydra as a basis for DTS is unclear. If Hydra will be used in the future, for example, it would be an option to explicitly define the classes `dts:Collection` and `dts:Navigation` subclasses of `hydra:Collection` (see Fig. 14). This alignment would formalize the relationship but might not be the intended design of the DTS maintainers, as it could impose unnecessary constraints in comparison to defining the property `member`, but also the data properties `title` and `description` independently from Hydra.

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.hydra-cg.com/spec/latest/core/>

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Fig. 14: Assumed Class Hierarchy in DTS as based on Hydra

The example of carrying over (intentionally or not) the semantics of Hydra also point to the general challenge of making sure that re-used ontologies are compatible amongst each other. In the context of DraCor, which already has a RDF ontology describing the responses from its API¹⁰⁹, understanding the underlying ontology of DTS is crucial to ensure semantic compatibility. DraCor's ontology is derived from the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model¹¹⁰, where a response from the API is considered a subclass of the class `dig:D1 Digital Object` of the CIDOC-CRM extension "CRMdig"¹¹¹. This means that every API response is treated as a digital object, adhering to the principles and definitions set forth by CIDOC-CRM and its superclass `crm:E73 Information Object`. Given this foundation, it is essential to avoid any semantic incompatibilities when integrating the Distributed Text Services (DTS) Specification with DraCor. This lack of definition makes it difficult to anticipate and mitigate potential semantic conflicts.

Additionally, on the level of the instances, some objects in the current implementation result in blank nodes, which are then not easily linkable because they lack an unique identifier

¹⁰⁹ https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/blob/main/v1/dracor_api_ontology.ttl

¹¹⁰ <https://cidoc-crm.org/>

¹¹¹ <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmDIG>

(URI) in `@id`. This issue is particularly relevant for instances of the `CitableUnit` class – the “parts” a text is composed of which can be referenced via DTS. The absence of a unique identifier hinders the ability to effectively connect additional information to these outside of the DTS implementation. For example, in the case of DraCor DTS implementation individual scenes are represented by `CitableUnits` that, although having an identifier as a string value, do not have a full URI included and thus, we can not effectively address these entities when generating additional RDF with DraCor’s RDF module and storing these in the Jena Fuseki Triple Store.¹¹²

3.4.4 The DTS endpoints “Collection”, “Navigation”, and “Document”

Having discussed more general considerations and theoretical foundations of the DTS Specification, particularly in relation to Linked Data and its implications, we now shift our focus to a more practical perspective: In this part, we will delve into the other DTS endpoints (Collection, Navigation and Document), providing practical examples and demonstrations of how these endpoints can be utilized within DraCor. By exploring real-world use cases and specific functionalities, we aim to illustrate the tangible benefits and capabilities that the DTS implementation brings to the DraCor platform.

api/v1/dts/collection (DraCor DTS Collection Endpoint)

This endpoint allows users to access information about the “collections” available. Users can retrieve a list of available corpora, including metadata such as title, corpus maintainer, and corpus language, similar to the regular DraCor API endpoints `api/v1/corpora` and `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}`. This is useful for discovering and selecting specific collections for further exploration or analysis. For example, to list all available corpora, the following request URL can be used:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection>

However, through the Collection endpoint, users can not only access lists of available drama corpora but also retrieve detailed metadata for individual resources, i.e. plays. This functionality is similar to the regular DraCor endpoint

`api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}`.

To control this behaviour of the endpoint, the specification defines three query parameters for the Collection endpoint `id`, `nav` and `page`, whereas the DraCor implementation does not provide the paging functionality and therefore the parameter `page` is not available.

Parameter `id`: The query parameter `id` is used to identify a collection or a single resource, i.e. in the case of DraCor either a corpus or a single play. The value of the parameter should be a URI, which, in the case of DraCor can either be the corpus name (Feature C1: `corpus_name`,

¹¹² For a more detailed description of the problem see the corresponding GitHub issue: <https://github.com/distributed-text-services/specifications/issues/274>.

https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#corpus_name), e.g. `ger` of the *German Drama Corpus*, or a http(s) URI, e.g. <https://dracor.org/id/ger>.

We encourage using full HTTP-URIs when possible, because in most Linked Data applications this type of unique identifiers are commonly used. In the case of DraCor http(s) URIs will properly dereference in accordance with the concept of Cool URIs for the Semantic Web¹¹³. For a user this means, that navigating to the given URI with a web browser will show the HTML page with information on the play, e.g. <https://dracor.org/id/ger000088> will be redirected to <https://dracor.org/ger/lessing-emilia-galotti>.

If a Linked Data aware client requests RDF of the server for the URI using the HTTP Accept Header including the XML serialization of RDF `application/rdf+xml` the server will send a 303 “See other” HTTP Status code and provide the URL of the RDF serialization in the Location field of the response header. In the case of the play Emilia Galotti this is <https://dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/lessing-emilia-galotti/rdf>.

Parameter `nav`: This query parameter can be used to navigate the collection hierarchy. It can take on a single value only – `parents`. When supplied the Collection endpoint returns not the included sub-collections or resources in the `member` array, but the parent collection. For example, when requesting information on the German Shakespeare Drama Corpus (GershDraCor) and providing the `nav`, the API includes the metadata on the root collection “DraCor Corpora”:
<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/gersh&nav=parents>

```
{
  "@context" :
  "https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/context/1-alpha1.js
  on",
  "@id" : "https://staging.dracor.org/id/gersh",
  "@type" : "Collection",
  "dtsVersion" : "unstable",
  "totalParents" : 1,
  "totalChildren" : 38,
  "title" : "German Shakespeare Drama Corpus",
  "description" : "Edited by [Frank Fischer] (https://lehkost.github.io/). This
  corpus contains all 37 of Shakespeare's plays in their German translations
  published by Schlegel and Tieck, in the edition of Aufbau-Verlag Berlin/Weimar
  (3rd edition 1975), which is based on the last edition published during
  Schlegel's lifetime (3rd edition 1843/44). The digitised print edition was
  procured from [Zeno.org] (http://www.zeno.org/nid/20005683920) (via TextGrid
```

¹¹³ See <https://www.w3.org/TR/cooluris/>.

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Repository), which also provided an additional play («Die beiden edlen Vettern») that Shakespeare is now considered to have co-authored. For a full description please see the [README on GitHub] (<https://github.com/dracor-org/gershdracor>).",

```
"member" : [ {
  "@id" : "https://staging.dracor.org",
  "@type" : "Collection",
  "dtsVersion" : "unstable",
  "totalParents" : 0,
  "totalChildren" : 26,
  "title" : "DraCor Corpora"
} ]
}
```

The JSON-LD response of the API is – in this case a `Collection` object (see value of property `@type`). Without the parameter `nav` supplied, and the parameter `id` having as its value the identifier of a existing corpus, e.g. <https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat> for the Tatar Drama Corpus, the API returns a `Collection` object with information on this corpus. Metadata on the plays of this corpus are included as `Resource` objects in the `member` array. The following request URL can be used to fetch information on the Tatar Drama Corpus:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat>

The following example shows the returned data (we excluded the individual plays, see placeholder [...]):

```
{
  '@context':
  'https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/context/1-alpha.js
  on',
  '@id': 'https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat',
  '@type': 'Collection',
  'dtsVersion': 'unstable',
  'totalParents': 1,
  'totalChildren': 3,
  'title': 'Tatar Drama Corpus',
```

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```
'description': 'Edited by Daniil Skorinkin and Frank Fischer. Features a
handful of plays in Tatar language, provided through Tatar Electronic
Library.',

'member': [...],

'extensions' : {...}

}
```

The properties `@context`, `@id` and `@type` are key components of the JSON-LD standard.

The JSON-LD context linked in `@context` can be used (by a client) to expand the other property names included in the response object to full URIs. This mapping allows applications to understand the semantics of the terms by referencing their definitions in an ontology. How this works can be explained with the property “title” that is included in the response of the Collection endpoint.

With the help of the JSON-LD context that includes the mapping

```
"title": "hydra:title"
```

and the definition of the prefix `hydra: as`

```
"hydra": "https://www.w3.org/ns/hydra/core#"
```

allows a client to expand the property name `title` to

```
https://www.w3.org/ns/hydra/core#title.
```

This full URI refers to the term “title” as defined in the Hydra Core Vocabulary. Hydra is available as an OWL Ontology and defines its terms accordingly. A client can use the URI of the term `title` to retrieve the definition of the term, which is included in the Hydra Core Vocabulary as a Data Property.

The other two property that re-used from the Hydra Core Vocabulary contained in the `Collection` object returned by the DTS Collection endpoint are `hydra:description` (see <https://www.hydra-cg.com/spec/latest/core/#hydra:description>), a specialized sub-property of the more general `rdfs:comment` and the object property `hydra:member` that in DTS, in case of the Collection endpoint, is used to include either sub-collections or resources as parts of a collection.

Specific to DTS are the properties `dtsVersion`, `totalParents`, `totalChildren` and `extensions` that are returned as part of the `Collection` object in the DraCor DTS implementation. There are additional properties that are defined by the DTS Specification, but are not used (see <https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/versions/unstable/#scheme-for-collection-api-responses>). The used properties contain the following information:

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totalParents: This property contains the number of parent collections the current collection (or Resource) is part of. In the example from the Tatar Drama Corpus the number is 1 (as for all other corpora in DraCor), because the collection hierarchy of DraCor is flat: all corpora are part of a single parent collection that is “DraCor corpora”. Plays are always members of a single corpus only. Therefore the value of this always equals 1 when requesting a play via the Collection endpoint.

totalChildren: This property contains the number of resources that are children of the given collection. In the case of the Tatar Drama Corpus the number is 3, which means that there are three plays contained in this corpus. In case of a single play the value of the property is always 0.

member: This property links the collection with the data on the resources contained therein. In the case of the JSON-LD response of Tatar Drama Corpus the “members” are included as instances of the class `Resource` (`dts:Resource`) as items of an JSON array.

The following example shows the first item:

```
{ '@id': 'https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat000001',
  '@type': 'Resource',
  'title': 'Беренче театр',
  'totalParents': 1,
  'totalChildren': 0,
  'dublinCore': { 'language': 'tat', 'creator': 'Камал, Галиәсгар' },
  'document':
  'https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat000001{&ref,start,end,mediaType}',
  'navigation':
  'https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat000001{&ref,start,end,down}',
  'collection':
  'https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat000001{&nav}',
  'download':
  'https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/tat/plays/qamal-berenche-teatr/tei',
  'extensions': { '@context':
  'https://raw.githubusercontent.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/refs/heads/main/json-ld-contexts/dts-extension-context.json',
  'numOfSegments': 13,
  'yearNormalized': 1908,
```

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```
'wordCountText': 4505,
'numOfSpeakers': 7,
'wikidataUri': 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25556355'}}
```

The items which represent the plays in a given DraCor corpus are included as `Resource` objects. This is marked by the value of the property `@type`, which is `"Resource"`. Some of the other properties that appear on the `Resource` object have already been discussed above.

The properties `collection`, `navigation` and `document` contain URI Templates based on which a client can construct URLs to access the resource via the `Collection`, the `Navigation` and the `Document` endpoints.

The pattern listing the parameters is slightly different than the ones described when discussing the `Entrypoint` above: The URI Templates already include a fixed query parameter `resource` which holds the identifier of the given resource, e.g.

`?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat000001`, the other available query parameters are put in curly brackets `{}` with an ampersand `&` before the first parameter name, e.g. in the URI Template of the `document` endpoint: `{&ref,start,end,mediaType}`. When expanding the pattern to a full URL a client should for each parameter name create a sequence of ampersand `&`, parameter name, equals sign `=` and supplied value of the given parameter.

For example, when a client wants to use the `Document` endpoint to request the text proper of the first scene of the first act. This segment is identified by the fragment identifier `body/div[1]/div[1]` which must be provided as the value of the `ref` parameter. If a client wants to retrieve the content of this fragment as plaintext, this can be controlled in the request by setting the value of the parameter `mediaType` to `text/plain`. Accordingly, the variables in URI Template

```
{&ref,start,end,mediaType}
```

can be expanded into

```
&ref=body/div[1]/div[1]&mediaType=text/plain
```

and thus resulting in the following request URL:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat00001&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]&mediaType=text/plain](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/tat00001&ref=body/div[1]/div[1]&mediaType=text/plain)

Another property included in the `Resource` object is `download`. It holds a link to download the resource – in the case of DraCor it is the URL of the API endpoint that serves the TEI file `api/v1/copora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/tei`.

Metadata can be added to a resource in two sections or “metadata zones” (Almas et al. 2023). The `Metadata` objects are connected to the resource with the properties `dublinCore` and `extensions`. While in the first `Metadata` object terms of the Dublin Core Vocabulary (DC

Terms)¹¹⁴ can be used, the latter `Metadata` object connected via `extensions` that can hold additional metadata using terms of arbitrary schemas. The terms must be defined in a separate JSON-LD context.

The DraCor implementation adds additional metadata in `extensions`. The respective terms are included in a JSON-LD context that is currently available from a DraCor GitHub repository at <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/refs/heads/main/json-ld-contexts/dts-extension-context.json>, but will be later provided directly via the DraCor infrastructure to be properly dereferencable. In the JSON-LD context properties already defined in the DraCor API Ontology¹¹⁵ are used. However, In the current version of the DraCor DTS implementation only a couple of specialized data properties are present, as is shown in the following example:

```
{
  "@context":
  "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/refs/heads/main/json-ld-contexts/dts-extension-context.json",
  "numOfSegments": 13,
  "yearNormalized": 1908,
  "wordCountText": 4505,
  "numOfSpeakers": 7,
  "wikidataUri": "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25556355"
}
```

The following list includes the links to the descriptions of the respective API features referenced in the context:

- `numOfSegments`: Feature P37 `play_num_of_segments`, https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_num_of_segments
- `yearNormalized`: Feature P27 `play_year_normalized`, https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_year_normalized
- `wordCountText`: Feature P41 `play_num_of_word_tokens_in_text_elements`, https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_num_of_word_tokens_in_text_elements
- `numOfSpeakers`: Feature P45 `play_num_of_speakers`, https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_num_of_speakers
- `wikidataUri`: Here no Feature defined in the DraCor API Ontology could be re-used. The full URI included here is based on Feature P4 `play_wikidata_id`, https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#play_wikidata_id prepended by the Wikidata Base URI <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>

Because it is possible to attach custom metadata as well to a collection as to a resource via the `extensions` property, it is possible to cover the functionality provided by the DraCor APIs

¹¹⁴ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms>

¹¹⁵ https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/blob/main/v1/dracor_api_ontology.ttl

endpoints `api/v1/corpora`, `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}`, `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata` and, to some extent also endpoints, that provide metadata on a single play, e.g. `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}`.

When requesting metadata on a corpus via the `Collection` endpoint, the plays included in this corpus are listed in the `member` array, but, as has been said, it is also possible to retrieve metadata on a single play via the `Collection` endpoint. The following request URL can be used to fetch the data on the play “Lessing: Emilia Galotti” from the German Drama Corpus:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000088>

A single `Resource` object – not `Collection` as in the case of a corpus – is returned by the API that represents the play. It still resembles the objects included as members of the collection that was shown in the previous example from the Tatar Drama Corpus, but includes an additional nested object: the “Citation Tree”.

Citation Tree

A “Citation Tree” in the context of DTS refers to the hierarchical structure used to identify and reference specific parts of a text. This structure allows for the organization of textual content into so-called “Citable Units”, which can be cited and navigated.

The “Citation Tree” serves as an abstraction or generalization of the structure of a play, providing a standardized way to represent and navigate its hierarchical components, such as acts, scenes, speech acts and stage directions. Citation trees are essential for scholarly referencing, allowing researchers to accurately point to specific parts of a text. In the `Collection` endpoint (but also the `Navigation` endpoint) `CitationTree` objects are included for `Resources`. The property `citeStructure` is used for nesting child `CiteStructure` objects in the parent object. Fig. 15 contains a schematic of this data structure.

Fig. 15: Data Structure Citation Tree

In the case of the DraCor implementation of DTS a single “Citation Tree” is included as a `CitationTree` object in the JSON array with the key `citationTrees`.

It organizes a text into nested sections, such as the top level divisions front matter (identifier: `front`), text proper (`body`) and back matter (`back`) on the upper most level. A Citation Tree of a text that has only these divisions is one level deep and allows only for the retrieval of the before mentioned sections. It has a so-called maximum cite depth (deprecated¹¹⁶ property `maxCiteDepth`) of 1.

The text proper of texts on DraCor are commonly structured into nested segments, most prominently, but not always referred to as “acts” and “scenes”. There are common different labels depending on language and dramatic traditions, e.g. “configuration”¹¹⁷.

A play that is structured into scenes only – and these scenes could be addressed and retrieved via the DTS implementation – would have a maximum cite depth of 2.

If a play is divided into acts and therein into scenes the cite depth would be 3. In the current DraCor implementation it is possible to address segments of the play down to the level of the individual speech act and the stage direction, thus we support a maximum cite depth of 4 in the text proper.

The following code snippet shows the CitationTree object with the `@type` property value `CitationTree` is included in the play “Emilia Galotti” requested with the URL above:

```
"citationTrees" : [ {
  "@type" : "CitationTree",
  "maxCiteDepth" : 4,
  "citeStructure" : [ {
    "@type" : "CiteStructure",
    "citeType" : "front",
    "citeStructure" : [ {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "title_page"
    } ]
  } ],
  {
    "@type" : "CiteStructure",
    "citeType" : "body",
    "citeStructure" : [ {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "act",
      "citeStructure" : [ {
        "@type" : "CiteStructure",
        "citeType" : "scene",
        "citeStructure" : [ {
          "@type" : "CiteStructure",
          "citeType" : "speech"
        } ],
        {
          "@type" : "CiteStructure",
          "citeType" : "stage_direction"
        }
      ]
    } ]
  } ]
} ]
```

¹¹⁶ According to the changelog in the DTS specification the property `maxCiteDepth` was removed on 2004-08-08 (actually, this should be 2024-08-08).

¹¹⁷ See the remarks in the ODD at <https://staging.dracor.org/doc/odd#TEI.div>

```

    } ]
  } ]
} ]
} ]
} ]

```

This data structure can be visualized in the following tree diagram (Fig. 16):

Fig. 16: Schematic of the Citation Tree of the play *Lessing: Emilia Galotti*

From the `CitationTree` we can understand that the play “Emilia Galotti”:

- can be navigated, referenced, cited on four levels, the maximum cite depth is 4,
- on the top level the play is structured into two main parts: front matter and text proper (there is no back matter),
- the text proper is structured into acts and scenes,
- it is possible to address (reference, cite) individual speech acts or stage directions inside the scenes.

The `Collection` endpoint in the DTS API is primarily designed to facilitate the browsing of text collections, providing users with a catalog-like entry point to explore available resources.

However, in the context of the DraCor implementation, this endpoint goes beyond mere discovery functionality by including additional, DraCor-specific metadata in the `extensions` object which not only allow for filtering a corpus by certain criteria¹¹⁸ as is already possible with other DraCor API endpoints, e.g. `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}`, but can also be used to answer research questions specific to the study of drama.

Moreover, DTS specific metadata, like the information in the `CitationTree` object can become particularly relevant for scholars studying dramatic texts, as it provides a clear view of how plays are organized and segmented. Thus, the DraCor DTS `Collection` endpoint could enable comparative studies across multiple plays, allowing for the examination of structural patterns and their variations.¹¹⁹ This capability is invaluable for exploring how different playwrights approach the organization of their works and how these choices might influence the dramatic impact and audience engagement.

api/v1/dts/navigation (DraCor DTS Navigation endpoint)

While the `Collection` endpoint helps users locate individual resources within a collection – in the case of DraCor – a corpus, the DTS Navigation endpoint `/dts/navigation` returns data on the hierarchical relationships between different structural divisions of a text. It provides references that can be used to retrieve specific parts of the text from the DTS Document endpoint, enabling precise navigation and retrieval of text segments. It also lists available identifiers of these segments that can be used to unambiguously reference it.

DTS Specification defines the query parameters `resource`, `ref`, `start`, `end`, `down`, `tree` and `page`. Because the paging functionality has not been implemented in DraCor and there is only a single reference system in place (see explanation “CitationTree” above), the latter two parameters are not or not fully implemented in the DraCor endpoint.

Parameter `resource`: This query parameter is used to provide the unique identifier (URI) of the `Resource` being navigated. In the case of DraCor it is the HTTP-URI of a document that is also used as the value of the parameter `id` in the `Collection` endpoint. E.g. the identifier `https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000088` is used in the request to the `Collection` endpoint

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000088>

This same identifier should be used as the value of the parameter `resource` of the `Navigation` endpoint to navigate the structural segments of this play. For a request to the server to be valid

¹¹⁸ See examples in the section “Practical Examples using the data returned by the DraCor DTS `Collection` endpoint” of the accompanying Jupyter notebook published in the `dracor-notebooks` GitHub Repository <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks/tree/main/dts>.

¹¹⁹ See section “Practical example: Evaluating Structure as CitationTrees” in the Jupyter Notebook.

it is not sufficient to use the parameter `resource` alone, but in combination with the following parameters.

Parameter `ref`: This query parameter is used to supply an identifier of a certain segment of a text (a *Citable Unit*). The parameter `ref` must not be combined in a request with the parameters `start` and/or `end`.

DraCor Fragment Identifiers: The specification does not restrict what this identifier should be or how it should be minted. In the DraCor implementation these text fragment identifiers resemble XPath expressions. XPath is a W3C recommended language¹²⁰ used to navigate and select nodes within XML documents. Using XPath expressions, users can address resources or nodes within an XML tree by specifying paths that traverse the hierarchical structure of the document. The slash character `/` is used to separate the different levels or steps in a path expression, allowing to navigate down the hierarchical structure of XML. For example in the following XML snippet the element with the text value B can be "reached" starting from the element `<root>` and going down into the first nested element and then into the second nested element, which results in the path: `/root/element[1]/element[2]`

```
<root>
  <element>
    <element>A</element>
  </element>
  <element>B</element>
</root>
```

In the DraCor DTS implementation a similar notation is used to address segments of the text, that are – in the source TEI-XML File more deeply nested than in the simple example above:

```
<TEI>
  <teiHeader>
    <!-- ... -->
  </teiHeader>
  <text>
    <front>
      <div>
        <!-- ... -->
      </div>
    </front>
    <body>
      <div type="act">
        <head>First act</head>
        <div type="scene">
          <head>First scene</head>
          <stage>
```

¹²⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/xpath20>

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```

        <!-- ... -->
    </stage>
    <sp>
        <!-- ... -->
    <sp>
</div>
<div>
    <head>Second scene</head>
    <!-- ... -->
</div>
</div>
<div>
    <head>Second act</head>
    <!-- ... -->
</div>
<body>
</text>
</TEI>

```

A valid xPath expression to select the single first speech act in the first scene of the first act would be:

```
/TEI[1]/text[1]/body[1]/div[1]/div[1]/sp[1]
```

However, if we assume, that some of the elements (<TEI>, <text> and <body>) are included only once in a (DraCor) TEI file, the number in brackets – [1] – meaning the position in a sequence of sibling elements does not necessarily needs to be included. Thus, the xPath results in

```
/TEI/text/body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[1]
```

In the DraCor DTS implementation this whole xPath would no be used as identifier, but only the part starting from the element <text>. This results in an identifier used as the value of the parameter `ref` of

```
body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[1]
```

Likewise, the whole second act in the example above would be identified with `body/div[2]` and so on.

Parameters `start` and `end`: By using the Navigation endpoint it is possible to either address a single Citable Unit or a segment of the text, consisting of all Citable Unites between two nodes. When requesting this range of text, the parameters `start` and `end` include the identifiers of the Citable Units that define the boundaries of this sequence. It encompasses all Citable Units between these two points, including the starting and ending points themselves.

Requesting ranges is still an experimental feature in the DraCor implementation. A limitation is that the starting and ending points of a requested range must share the same parent. For example, a user can request the first three acts of a five-act play, or the second to seventh speeches within the second scene of the third act. However, he or she cannot request a range that spans from the last scene of the first act to the second scene of the third act, as these do not share a common parent.

Parameter `down`: This query parameter controls to which maximum depth the citation subtree should be returned. The depth is relative to the specified reference (identified with `ref` or `start` and `end`), e.g. if a resource is 4 levels deep (body, act, scene, speech act/stage direction) then a value of 2 of the parameter `down` and starting from the body (`ref=body`), the Navigation endpoint returns all acts and all scenes therein. When starting from the first act (`ref=body/div[1]`) it would return all scenes from the first act only including speech acts and stage directions.

A value of `-1` indicates that the entire citation tree, down to its deepest level, should be returned. If the parameter is not set, the Navigation endpoint will not return any Citable Units of the Citation tree, but only the references identified by `ref` or `start` and `end`.

The following request url can be used to retrieve a single play via the Navigation endpoint. Apart from the mandatory parameter `resource` which holds the ID of the play, as a bare minimum it is necessary to provide either a reference to a citable unit as the value of the `ref` parameter or the parameter `down` specifying down to which level citable units should be returned. In the following example information about the first act (`ref=body/div[1]`) of *Goethe: Iphigenie auf Tauris* (<https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001>) are requested:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[1\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1])

The DTS Navigation endpoint returns a `Navigation` object (see `@type` property), identified with the request URL as the value of the `@id` property. The property `dtsVersion` holds the version of the DTS Specification, that is the basis for the response object. Additionally, it includes a `Resource` object (linked via property `resource`) as well as a reference to a Citable Unit (property `ref`) (in the following example replaced with placeholder `{ ... }`):

```
{
  "@context" :
  "https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications/context/1-alpha1.json",
  "@id" :
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1]",
  "@type" : "Navigation",
  "dtsVersion" : "unstable",
  "resource" : { ... } ,
}
```

```
"ref" : { ... }
}
```

The included `Resource` object lists the URI Templates for the Document, the Collection and the Navigation endpoints (properties `document`, `collection`, `navigation`), the Citation Tree(s) (property `citationTrees`) and – as in optional property (`mediaType`) carries the information in which formats the resource is available:

```
"resource" : {
  "@id" : "https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001",
  "@type" : "Resource",
  "document" :
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001{&ref,start,end,mediaType}",
  "collection" :
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001{&nav}",
  "navigation" :
  "https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001{&ref,start,end,down}",
  "citationTrees" : [ ... ],
  "mediaTypes" : [ "application/tei+xml", "text/plain" ]
}
```

When requesting information on a single citable unit providing its identifier in the query parameter `ref` the returned data includes this referenced citable unit. It is linked with the property `ref`:

```
"ref" : {
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "body/div[1]",
  "level" : 2,
  "parent" : "body",
  "citeType" : "act",
  "dublinCore" : {
    "title" : "Erster Aufzug"
  }
}
```

The `CitableUnit` object has the following properties:

- **@type**: This JSON-LD specific property indicates the class of the object. The only allowed value is `CitableUnit`.
- **identifier**: The identifier of the citable unit. It is used as the value of `ref` to identify it across the Navigation and Document endpoints. In the DraCor implementation xPath-like path expressions are used as identifiers (see DraCor Fragment Identifiers above)

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- **level**: This property indicates the depth at which the citable unit is found within the citation tree of the Resource.
- **parent**: This property contains the identifier of the parent of the citable unit in the tree of the Resource
- **citeType**: This property contains a string identifying the type of the citable unit, e.g. "act", "scene", "speech", "stage_direction". The values correspond to the types used in the `CiteStructure` objects in the `CitationTree`.
- **dublinCore**: This property is used to include a `Metadata` object using terms from the *Dublin Core Terms Vocabulary*. In the DraCor implementation currently only the term `dct:title` is used. In acts and scenes it includes the value of the very first `<tei:head>` element found in the corresponding `<tei:div>`.
- **extensions**: This property is used to include a `MetadataObject` with DraCor-specific properties.

The following examples illustrate how to use the Navigation endpoint to retrieve information about a single play.¹²¹

The following request Url can be used to retrieve the top level structural segments of the play Goethe: "Iphigenie auf Tauris" (`ger000001`) from the German Drama Corpus. Setting the query parameter `down` to the value of `1` tells the API to get the structural segments one level deep. Because the parameter `ref` is not used, the starting point is the top most element of the tree – the whole text:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&down=1>

The Navigation object returned by the API includes a property `member` which holds an array including two citable units – the front matter (identifier: `front`) and the text proper (identifier: `body`):

```
"member" : [ {
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "front",
  "level" : 1,
  "parent" : null,
  "citeType" : "front"
}, {
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "body",
  "level" : 1,
  "parent" : null,
  "citeType" : "body"
```

¹²¹ A more detailed and executable version can be found in the Jupyter Notebook <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks/tree/main/dts>.

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```
} ]
```

The values of the `identifier` properties can be used to construct request urls to retrieve information about these parts of the text. For example, the request URL to retrieve all structural divisions of the front matter can be constructed by using the value of the property `identifier` of the first included citable unit `front` as the value of the query parameter `ref` (`ref=front`) and setting the parameter `down` to the value `-1` to tell the API to include all nested structural segments down to the lowest level in the citation tree:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&&ref=front&down=-1>

The response includes four citable units, of which one represents the *dramatis personae* (`"citeType" : "dramatis_personae"`):

```
{
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "front/div[2]",
  "level" : 2,
  "parent" : "front",
  "citeType" : "dramatis_personae"
}
```

Again, the `identifier` of this citable unit could be used in further requests to the API to retrieve information about this segment, or get the textual content from the Document endpoint. When citing this fragment, the link to the navigation endpoint including its identifier value as the `ref` parameter, could be used:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=front/div\[2\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=front/div[2])

The Navigation endpoint can also be used to fetch the citable units down from a certain element of the text proper. To understand what is available we can have a look at the citation tree:

```
"citationTrees" : [ {
  "@type" : "CitationTree",
  "maxCiteDepth" : 4,
  "citeStructure" : [ {
    "@type" : "CiteStructure",
    "citeType" : "front",
    "citeStructure" : [ {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "front"
    } ], {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "dramatis_personae"
    }
  ]
}
```

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```

    }, {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "setting"
    } ]
  }, {
    "@type" : "CiteStructure",
    "citeType" : "body",
    "citeStructure" : [ {
      "@type" : "CiteStructure",
      "citeType" : "act",
      "citeStructure" : [ {
        "@type" : "CiteStructure",
        "citeType" : "scene",
        "citeStructure" : [ {
          "@type" : "CiteStructure",
          "citeType" : "speech"
        }, {
          "@type" : "CiteStructure",
          "citeType" : "stage_direction"
        } ]
      } ]
    } ]
  } ]
} ]
} ]
} ]
} ]

```

The text proper is structured as is shown in the tree below¹²²:

```

Body
├── Act
│   ├── Scene
│   │   ├── Speech
│   │   └── Stage direction

```

We could now list the top level structural elements of the text proper – the acts:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body&down=1>

Or, start from a structural segment, e.g. the first act (`body/div[1]`) and list the scenes with `down=1`:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[1\]&down=1](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1]&down=1)

¹²² These trees can be generated on the basis of the CitationTree objects, see Jupyter Notebook for examples.

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There are four scenes in the first act of which the following example shows the second scene (`body/div[1]/div[2]`):

```
{
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "body/div[1]/div[2]",
  "level" : 3,
  "parent" : "body/div[1]",
  "citeType" : "scene",
  "dublinCore" : {
    "title" : "Zweiter Auftritt"
  }
}
```

The `MetadataObject` included via the property `dublinCore` includes the title of the scene, which is “Zweiter Auftritt” (“Second Appearance”).

We can list the speech acts and stage directions in this scene by going down one level:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[2\]&down=1](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1]/div[2]&down=1)

Or, starting from the parent segment, the first act, list all the scenes as well as the speech acts and stage directions by setting the parameter `down` to 2, i.e. going down two levels from the level of the act:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[1\]&down=2](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1]&down=2)

The same result is achieved by setting `down` to `-1` because this will include all nested citable units down to the very bottom of the tree:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[1\]&down=-1](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[1]&down=-1)

The parameter `down` can also be used as the only additional parameter provided. Setting it to `-1` will result in just listing each and every citable unit of the resource:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&down=-1>

The citable units representing the individual speech acts include additional DraCor-specific metadata in the `extensions` field. The following example shows a single speech act with the identifier `body/div[2]/div[1]/sp[2]` from the first scene of the second act:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div\[2\]/div\[1\]/sp\[2\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&ref=body/div[2]/div[1]/sp[2])

```
{
  "@type" : "CitableUnit",
  "identifier" : "body/div[2]/div[1]/sp[2]",
  "level" : 4,
  "parent" : "body/div[2]/div[1]",
  "citeType" : "speech",
  "extensions" : {
    "@context" :
    "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology/refs/heads/main/json-ld-contexts/dts-extension-context.json",
    "speakers" : [ "pylades" ],
    "snippet" : "Ich bin noch nicht, Orest, [...] wöhnt."
  }
}
```

It contains additional information which character is speaking (property `speakers`) and includes a small portion of the text (property `snippet`). This text snippet consists of the first 5 word tokens of a speech, three dots to mark an ellipsis and the last word token. The snippet can help to identify a certain speech that should be further referenced; the information on the speaking characters can allow for filtering for certain speeches by a character.¹²³

Using the Navigation endpoint for analysis

We already argued that the `CitationTree` object can be repurposed to get information about the general structuring of a play, e.g. if a play is structured into acts only, or acts and scenes, if a play contains a dramatis personae in the front matter, and so on. The reliability of these information depends on the implementation of the functionality that computes the `CitationTree` based on the combination of TEI-XML elements like `<div>` and certain attributes¹²⁴.

The endpoints of the regular DraCor API already provide some information about the segmentation of a play. Foremost it is the count based metrics that provide insight into the number of acts and segments a play is divided into (API Feature P37 `play_num_of_segments`, API Feature P38 `play_num_of_acts`). These information is not provided by endpoints that return information on an individual play like `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}` or

¹²³ For practical examples of filtering based on certain criteria see Jupyter Notebook.

¹²⁴ see the code in the DTS module: `local:generate-citationTree` and especially `local:generate-citeStructure` which includes a lot of hard-coded logic: <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api/blob/a8ec727c13b3a8d43da298b77ac989572c5c20a4/modules/dts.xqm#L719-L870>

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`api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/play/{playname}/metrics` but needs to be extracted from the “metadata table” of a corpus or from the list of plays included in the response of the endpoint `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/metadata`. For the German Drama Corpus the data can be retrieved via

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/metadata/csv>

If a user is interested in the data of a single play only there is already some overhead of retrieving the information. For a reasonably big corpus as the German Drama Corpus, we need to fetch the data of all included plays (which takes some time, in this case almost 40 seconds) and then use some sort of filtering mechanism to just get the data on the single play.

Additional information on structure can be retrieved from another endpoint: The data returned by `api/v1/corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` includes a JSON array in the field `segments` that lists the individual structural segments that are the basis for generating the co-presence networks. To get this data for the play “Iphigenie auf Tauris” the following request URL can be used:

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/corpora/ger/plays/goethe-iphigenie-auf-tauris>

By combining the information gathered from requests to both endpoints mentioned above for the given play, a user can find out the following:

- there are "acts" in the play, because the value of the feature `play_num_of_acts` is greater than 0 or not null,
- the play is divided into 5 acts,
- there are 20 segments in the play,
- these segments are of the type "scene", and,
- which character(s) are speaking in which of these segments.

With some string analyzing it would be possible to retrieve the information which segment is included in which act because the values of title are constructed following the pattern `{title of act} | {title of scene}` relying on the text content of the element `<tei:head>` in the TEI-XML source.

The same information can be retrieved by the DTS API using the Navigation endpoint. If some client side filtering logic is applied later on it is sufficient to make a single request to the API at

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger/000001&ref=body&down=-1>

We can show that it is possible to retrieve the same information on the structuring of a play returned by various endpoints of the DraCor API using the DTS Navigation endpoint.¹²⁵ The functionalities of the endpoints complement each other, and, while the results are the same, the means of getting them differ greatly in performance and amount of necessary client-side post-processing.

Depending on the endpoint and the strategy chosen different performances are possible. In general, fetching data from the API is more resource intensive and, in some cases, takes a long time. For example, when a user wants to get the information on the number of acts and scenes of a single play only, getting this information from the `corpora/{corpusname}` endpoint takes almost 40 seconds for the German Drama Corpus. This is because the endpoint returns data on the whole corpus. In contrast, fetching the data from the DTS Navigation endpoint takes only 1.5 seconds, but produces an overhead client side because the values need to be computed afterwards.

In other cases, retrieving the same information from the DTS Navigation endpoint that is provided by the regular DraCor API can be realized by issuing multiple calls to the API, e.g. when retrieving and producing the same information on the segments of a play that is already returned ready to use from the `corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}` endpoint.¹²⁶

However, in its current implementation, with DTS we can address citable units down to a certain hierarchical level only. This limitation means that more granular structural units, such as nested stage directions¹²⁷ or individual verse lines within spoken text, are not yet addressable through the Navigation endpoint.

To fully leverage the potential of the DTS Navigation endpoint for the analysis of Drama, there is a need to extend its capabilities to also include deeper nested structural units. By making elements like individual verse lines and nested stage directions addressable, researchers would gain the ability to analyze and navigate plays at an even more detailed level.

We have also seen that there is a need for client-side processing, such as assembling the speakers of a structural unit (like a scene or act) by fetching or extracting the speakers from individual speech acts. This process would likely require adding information about speaking characters to structural units that currently do not include a `speaker` property in the `extensions` metadata object. By enhancing the DraCor-specific metadata to include this information, researchers would be better equipped to analyze and navigate plays at a more detailed level, without the need of much post-processing.

Citing plays with DTS

In the preceding sections, we explored how the DTS Navigation endpoint can be effectively used for the structural analysis of a play, providing detailed insights into its organization and hierarchical components. However, beyond its analytical utility, the DTS Navigation endpoint

¹²⁵ See Jupyter Notebook.

¹²⁶ The same segment information can also be generated client-side based on a single API call, i.e. <https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&do wn=-1>, but makes some more complex data wrangling necessary.

¹²⁷ see examples in the Jupyter notebook.

offers an additional functionality that is central to the study of drama: the possibility to cite a specific part of a play.

One of core ideas behind DTS is to enhance the citability of digital texts, a feature particularly valuable in the realm of Digital Drama research. Unlike prose, where citations in the literature often rely on page numbers, drama research benefits from referencing the text's structural divisions. This allows for more precise citations, normally referencing a specific act, a scene within, and, if available the verse lines within a play. The fine-grained citation capability of the DraCor DTS implementation aligns with the traditional methods of referencing dramatic texts and thus, could support more nuanced scholarly analysis in Computational Literary Studies.

DraCor has already significantly advanced the digital citation of drama by enabling references to entire plays using unique identifiers (URIs). For example, the play "Iphigenie auf Tauris" can be cited using the URI <https://dracor.org/id/ger000001> because the DraCor identifier, the Play ID (Feature P2 `play_id`) is universally unique across all DraCor corpora.

Additionally, DraCor has introduced unique identifiers for characters within a single play, which, when combined with the play's identifier, create potentially universally unique identifiers as well. Although these character identifiers are not yet resolvable via the `/id/{id}` endpoint (see API Documentation), they represent a step toward more precise and standardized citation practices in dramatic research.

The following examples illustrate how the DTS Navigation endpoint facilitates the citation of dramatic texts. They are taken from the english translation of Manfred Pfister's important work "Das Drama" ("The Theory and Analysis of Drama", engl. translation by John Halliday), which has been foundational for the structuralist approach to drama studies and has inspired research in the Computational Literary Studies.

In the chapter on "dramatic irony" Pfister refers to a scene from the play *Shakespeare: Julius Caesar*:

Thus, one of the most famous examples of irony in all drama - Antony's spoken refrain 'Brutus is an honourable man' in his funeral oration for the central figure in **Shakespeare's Julius Caesar (III, ii)** - has nothing to do with dramatic irony in the strict sense since it is a verbal utterance that the speaker intended to be ironic, and whose irony is intended to be, and indeed does become, obvious to the fictional receivers. (Pfister 2000: 56)

The reference "Shakespeare's Julius Caesar (III, ii)" in the text refers to the play Julius Caesar, which is contained in DraCor as the play with the identifier `shake000030`, although in a different edition stemming from the Folger Digital Library (for the integration of this corpus into DraCor and possible use cases in combining APIs see also D7.1, chapter 6.1 "Relating APIs using OpenAPI: The Example of the Folger Shakespeare API").

In the reference the roman capital letters "III" stand for the third act, the small roman letters "ii" mean the second scene of the play. This scene of the play can be addressed via the DTS Navigation endpoint setting the value of the parameter `ref` to `body/div[3]/div[2]`, which results in the URL:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div\[3\]/div\[2\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div[3]/div[2])

The larger part of the speech of Anthony is starting with the Citable Unit with the identifier `body/div[3]/div[2]/sp[31]`, in which the phrase "Brutus is an honourable man" is frequently repeated. This citable unit can be addressed as such:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div\[3\]/div\[2\]/sp\[31\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div[3]/div[2]/sp[31])

In the example above, Pfister referred to a single scene without pointing to a certain speech act in particular, but there are also cases, in which there is a reference to a certain portion text below the scene level in another Shakespearean play:

[I]n the sphere of verbal communication there are speeches that have scarcely any novelty value for the fictional listener on stage, but which serve to clarify certain relationships for the audience [...] An example of this is Prospero's report on Ariel's past in **The Tempest (I,ii,250—93)**; this contains no information that could possibly be unfamiliar to Ariel, but it is new, and thus important, to the audience.
(Pfister 2000: 40)

Obviously, the reference in the text refers to *Shakespeare: The Tempest* which is contained in DraCor as the play with the identifier `shake000001`. As in the example from Julius Ceasar, the reference `I,ii` refers to act and scene. In a request to the DTS Navigation endpoint setting the value of the parameter `ref` to have to be set to `body/div[1]/div[2]` for retrieving information on the given citable unit:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000001&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[2\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000001&ref=body/div[1]/div[2])

To list all speeches in this section, we can use the parameter `down` with a value of `1` to get the speeches included in the `member` property:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000001&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[2\]&down=1](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000001&ref=body/div[1]/div[2]&down=1)

Beyond that, really identifying the actual part of the scene, Pfister is pointing to, is difficult. He does not include a quotation from the text. Therefore it is not possible to search the response of the API to identify the portion of the text in the API response. The lines referenced with the numbers "250–93" refer to an edition he uses, that is not the same as the edition included in

DraCor. And even if the source of the text would be the same, still individual lines are currently not included as citable units and therefore not directly addressable.

Below is another example that does not include a bibliographic reference, but includes a literal citation of a parts of the play "The Cherry Orchard" by Anton Chekhov:

Stage-directions are not restricted to the secondary text, however; they may also be found, implicitly, in the primary text - as the following extract from Chekhov's Cherry Orchard demonstrates:

LOPAKHIN: What's the matter, Dooniasha?

DOONIASHA: My hands are trembling. I feel as if I'm going to faint.

LOPAKHIN: You're too refined and sensitive, Dooniasha. You dress yourself up like a lady, and you do your hair like one too.

(Pfister 2000: 15–16)

The source of this citation is included in endnote 7 "A. Chekhov (1954) 334. [...]" which is according to the bibliography "Chekhov, A. The Cherry Orchard, in: Plays, transl. and with introd. by E. Feu (Harmondsworth, 1954)."

While there is no translation of the play Cherry Orchard by Anton Chekhov in DraCor, let alone the cited edition, we can still locate the original Russian play. It has the unique DraCor identifier `rus000059`.

All citable units of the play can be accessed via the Navigation endpoint at

<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/rus000059&ref=body&down=-1>

Based on the snippets and some guessing the cited passage can be found. The first speech in the Russian original has the fragment identifier `body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[7]` and thus can be retrieved at

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/rus000059&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]/sp\[7\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/rus000059&ref=body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[7]) .

Using the parameters `start` (value: `body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[7]`) and `end` (value `body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[9]`) all three speeches can be cited as a range with the following URL:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/rus000059&start=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]/sp\[7\]&end=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]/sp\[9\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/rus000059&start=body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[7]&end=body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[9])

The three examples above already show that there are several possibilities of how traditional scholarship cites and quotes the text of plays and that some of the functionality implemented allows to construct dereferenceable URIs for the cited segments.

Still, the resulting URIs are relatively long and not very "nice" to include in actual studies, an option would be to devise a shorter notation that could be then expanded into the full URI, e.g. `dracor:shake000030#body/div[3]/div[2]` – still quite long, but this would contain enough information to convert it into a full URI –

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div\[3\]/div\[2\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div[3]/div[2])

Locating a specific passage to cite can be quite cumbersome. Users must first examine the full text, such as in DraCor's front end in the "Full Text" tab, and guess which part of the text will appear in the snippet (5 first word tokens of a speech followed by an ellipsis and the last one). They then need to list all citable units with their snippets using the parameter `down=-1` and perform a full-text search (Ctrl+F) in the browser to locate the desired citable unit. After identifying the citable unit, they must copy the value of the identifier field and manually construct the link for the navigation endpoint. Implementing a graphical user interface (GUI) would significantly enhance this process, making it more intuitive and user-friendly.

`api/v1/dts/document` (DraCor DTS Document Endpoint)

The DTS Document endpoint is used to get a textual representation of a single Resource or parts thereof. The endpoint accepts the following query parameters:

Parameter `resource`: This query parameter is used to provide the unique identifier (URI) of the Resource of which a textual representation is requested. In the case of DraCor it is the HTTP URI of a document, e.g. It is the same value that would be used in a request to the Navigation endpoint and also as the value of the parameter `id` in case of the Collection endpoint. In requests to the Document endpoint providing this parameter is mandatory.

Parameter `ref`: This query parameter is used to supply an identifier of a certain segment of a text (a Citable Unit). The Document endpoint uses the same identifiers as the Navigation endpoint (see detailed description of the DraCor Fragment Identifiers there).

Parameters `start` and `end`: To request a textual representation of a section spanning across several structural units of the text, e.g. the first 5 scenes of the second act, the parameters `start` and `end` include the identifiers of the Citable Units that define the boundaries of a sequence.

Parameter `tree`: The DTS Specification foresees an optional parameter to provide the identifier of a Citation Tree that is not the default. This parameter is not implemented for DraCor because there is only one Citation Tree available.

Parameter `mediaType`: This parameter controls in which format the textual representation of a Resource is returned. By default the endpoint returns TEI-XML.

The DraCor DTS implementation provides TEI-XML in all cases, but also a plaintext representation requested with `text/plain` as the value of the `mediaType` parameter. Available formats are listed when requesting a Resource via the Collection or Navigation endpoints in the field `mediaTypes`.

The plaintext representation is currently not available for a range of citable units requested with the parameters `start` and `end`.

If a fragment is requested using the parameters `ref` or `start` and `end` the segment of the TEI-XML file is wrapped into a DTS custom element `<dts:wrapper>` (in the DTS namespace `https://w3id.org/dts/api#`) as shown in the following example requested via

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000243&ref=body/div\[19\]/sp\[3\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000243&ref=body/div[19]/sp[3])

```
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <dts:wrapper xmlns:dts="https://w3id.org/dts/api#">
    <sp who="#gretchen">
      <speaker>MARGARETE.</speaker>
      <lg>
        <l>Nun sag, wie hast du's mit der Religion?</l>
        <l>Du bist ein herzlich guter Mann,</l>
        <l>Allein ich glaub', du hältst nicht viel davon.</l>
      </lg>
    </sp>
  </dts:wrapper>
</TEI>
```

The same textual fragment can be retrieved as plaintext when setting the parameter `mediaType` to the value `text/plain`:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000243&ref=body/div\[19\]/sp\[3\]&mediaType=text/plain](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000243&ref=body/div[19]/sp[3]&mediaType=text/plain)

The parameters `start` and `end` can be used to request the text of a range of citable units:

[https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&start=body/div\[4\]/div\[2\]/sp\[7\]&end=body/div\[4\]/div\[2\]/sp\[14\]](https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001&start=body/div[4]/div[2]/sp[7]&end=body/div[4]/div[2]/sp[14])

The DTS Document endpoint provides a link (key `Link`) back to the Resource via the Collection endpoint in the HTTP headers¹²⁸:

¹²⁸ See Jupyter Notebook on how to access the headers with requests.

```
<https://staging.dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://staging.dracor.org/id/ger000001>; rel="collection"
```

This way, it is possible to go back from the textual representation to the actual resource the text is drawn from.

Evaluating Data Retrieval Capabilities: DraCor API vs. DraCor DTS API

In practical use cases the endpoints Collection, Navigation and Document are used together.

The experiments conducted for this report aim to compare the functionality and capabilities of the regular DraCor API with the newly implemented DTS API.¹²⁹ The focus is on determining whether the DTS API can replicate the data retrieval capabilities of the DraCor API, particularly in terms of accessing and manipulating textual data. The experiments involve practical use cases that demonstrate how the Navigation and Document endpoints of the DTS API can be utilized to achieve similar outcomes to those provided by the DraCor API.

The "regular" DraCor API provides several endpoints that allow to get a subset of the text:

- `corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/spoken-text`: Spoken text of a play excluding stage directions (and Speaker labels)
- `corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/spoken-text-by-character`: Spoken text for each character of a play
- `corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/stage-directions`: Stage directions of a play
- `corpora/{corpusname}/plays/{playname}/stage-directions-with-speakers`. In the result of this endpoint the stage directions that are nested into a `<sp>` element and can thus be attributed to a character are prepended with the speaker label.

The DTS API, on the other hand, offers a more flexible and granular approach to accessing textual data. It allows users to query structural information via the Navigation endpoint and retrieve text representations via the Document endpoint. This flexibility enables more precise and customized data retrieval, albeit with the need for additional post-processing.

One of the key experiments involved retrieving the spoken text of a play using both the DraCor API and the DTS API. The DraCor API provides a straightforward endpoint that returns the spoken text as plain text.

The DTS API, in contrast, requires a more complex process. Users must first query the Navigation endpoint to obtain structural information about the text, including citable units representing speech acts (value of the property `citeType` is `speech`). The identifiers of these citable units are then used to query the Document endpoint to retrieve the actual text in

¹²⁹ For executable code see the Jupyter notebook "Distributed Text Services (DTS) in DraCor" <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks/blob/main/dts/dts.ipynb>.

TEI-XML format. This process involves sending multiple requests to the API, which can be time-consuming and may not be suitable for front-end applications.

Despite the additional complexity, the experiments demonstrated that the DTS API can retrieve the same spoken text as the DraCor API, albeit with the need for post-processing to handle whitespace and newline characters.

Another experiment focused on retrieving the spoken text of individual characters. The DraCor API provides an endpoint that returns the spoken text for each character in a play, including additional information such as the character's identifier, label, gender, and roles.

The DTS API allows for a more granular approach by filtering citable units representing speech acts by specific characters. For example, the experiments demonstrated how to retrieve the spoken text of the character Iphigenie using the DTS API. This involved filtering the citable units for speech acts (value of the property `citeType` is `speech`) attributed to Iphigenie (`iphigenie` included in the array of the field `speakers`) and then querying the Document endpoint to retrieve the actual text.

The results showed that the text retrieved via the DTS API, after handling whitespace, was identical to the text returned by the DraCor API. However, the DTS API does not provide the additional character information that the DraCor API offers, such as gender and roles.

The experiments also explored the retrieval of stage directions using both APIs. The DraCor API provides endpoints that return stage directions, including those nested within `<sp>` elements. The DTS API, on the other hand, allows for the retrieval of stage directions by filtering citable units representing stage directions (value of the property `citeType` is `stage_direction`).

The experiments demonstrated that the DTS API can retrieve the same stage directions as the DraCor API, with the added flexibility of filtering by specific structural segments of the text, e.g. stage directions of the second act. This capability enables more precise and customized data retrieval, which is not possible with the DraCor API.

One of the significant advantages of the DTS API is its ability to provide structural information about the text. This information can be used to retrieve text representations for specific segments of the text, such as acts and scenes. The experiments demonstrated how to retrieve the spoken text of the character Iphigenie in a specific act and scene using the DTS API.

This level of flexibility is not possible with the DraCor API, which does not provide endpoints that return structural information in a way that can be reconnected to the text. The only option with the DraCor API is to rely on the returned TEI-XML, which requires additional parsing and processing.

The experiments conducted for this report highlight the strengths and limitations of both the DraCor API and the DTS API. While the DraCor API provides straightforward endpoints for retrieving specific subsets of textual data, the DTS API offers a more flexible and granular approach to accessing and manipulating textual data. This flexibility comes at the cost of additional complexity and the need for post-processing, but it enables more precise and customized data retrieval.

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The DTS API's ability to provide structural information and retrieve text representations for specific segments of the text makes it a powerful tool for researchers and developers working with dramatic corpora. However, the lack of additional character information and the need for multiple API requests are limitations that need to be addressed in future developments.

3.5 Widening the DraCor Tool Stack: “EzDrama” and “Who is?”

In the following, we present two tools that were developed in the context of work package 7 of the CLS INFRA project and that each automate sub-processes in the creation of DraCor XML files. The “EzDrama” tool was developed by Daniil Skorinkin; the “Who is?” tool was developed by Carsten Milling. We present both tools in the form of a question-led portrait.

3.5.1 EzDrama (Text: Daniil Skorinkin)

What is this tool?

EzDrama is a lightweight markup language designed specifically for encoding drama texts. It works as a middle layer between raw plain text and fully structured TEI/XML, allowing you to enrich theatrical scripts with minimal symbolic markers instead of writing verbose XML. The overall goal is to simplify the process of converting typed or scanned play scripts into standardized TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) format, making them ready for further use on DraCor.

Fig. 17: EzDrama Workflow

In essence, EzDrama is similar to a simplified Markdown or YAML format. It offers short, clear notations (e.g. @ for the speaker’s name, # for acts/scenes, \$ for stage directions) that keep source files legible for humans while facilitating straightforward automated transformations into TEI/XML.

What can it do?

EzDrama helps you structure a play into acts, scenes, speakers, speeches, and stage directions without forcing you to manually craft TEI tags. Once these short markers are applied, the script can be automatically or semi-automatically converted to a TEI-encoded XML file. Key capabilities include:

- **Marking Divisions:** Use #, ##, ###, etc. to indicate hierarchical divisions (acts, scenes, etc.).
- **Labeling Speakers:** Use @ lines to define speaker names and automatically generate `<sp who="# . . . ">` TEI tags.
- **Stage Directions:** Use \$ for multi-line stage directions or % for inline stage directions within a speech.

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- **Automatic Brackets Handling:** Parentheses within a speaker’s text can be automatically encoded as `<stage>` directions.
- **Metadata Inclusion:** Special markers like `@author`, `@title`, `@subtitle` embed relevant bibliographic data.
- **Page Breaks:** A simple pattern like `5 :` can be turned into a `<pb n="5" />` TEI tag.
- **Cast Lists:** Lines preceded by `^` go into a `<castList>` section.

By relying on these straightforward markers, EzDrama reduces time spent in manual tagging while preserving the document’s dramatic structure.

1) Raw input	2) EasyDrama markup	3) Auto-generated raw TEI
Ham	@title Ham	<code><TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"></code>
A tragedy	@subtitle A tragedy	<code><teiHeader></code>
By William S	@author William S	<code><fileDesc></code>
Dramatis Personae	^ Dramatis Personae	<code><titleStm></code>
Ham	Ham	<code><title type="main">Ham</title></code>
Egg	Egg	<code><title type="sub">A tragedy</title></code>
Vikings	Vikings	<code><author>William S</author></code>
Act 1	# Act 1	<code></titleStm></code>
Scene 1	## Scene 1	<code><publicationStm></code>
Ham: Lovely Spam!	@ Ham:	<code><publisher xml:id="draCor">DraCor</publisher></code>
Egg: Wonderful Spam!	Lovely Spam!	<code><idno type="URL">https://draCor.org/</idno></code>
Scene 2	@ Egg:	<code><availability></code>
Enter Vikings	Wonderful Spam!	<code><licence></code>
Ham: Egg, Spam!	## Scene 2	<code><ab>CC0 1.0</ab></code>
Sausage, and Bacon!	\$ Enter Vikings	<code><ref target="https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/"></code>
Vikings (singing):	@ Ham:	<code>Licence</ref></code>
Spam, Spam,(o!)	Egg, Spam!	<code></licence></code>
Spam, Spam, (loud)	Sausage, and Bacon!	<code></availability></code>
Spam, Spam, (quiet)	@ Vikings (singing):	<code></publicationStm></code>
Spam, and Spam	~Spam, Spam,(o!)	<code><sourceDesc></code>
The end	Spam, Spam, (loud)	<code><bibl type="digitalSource"></code>
	Spam, Spam, (quiet)	<code><name>ENTER SOURCE NAME HERE</name></code>
	Spam, and Spam	<code><idno type="URL">ENTER SOURCE URL HERE</idno></code>
	\$ The end	<code><availability status="free"></code>
		<code><p>In the public domain.</p></code>
		<code></availability></code>
		<code></bibl></code>
		<code></sourceDesc></code>
		<code></fileDesc></code>
		<code><profileDesc></code>
		<code><particDesc></code>
		<code><listPerson></code>
		<code><person xml:id="egg"></code>
		<code><persName>Egg</persName></code>
		<code></person></code>
		<code><person xml:id="ham"></code>
		<code><persName>Ham</persName></code>
		<code></person></code>
		<code><person xml:id="vikings"></code>
		<code><persName>Vikings</persName></code>
		<code></person></code>
		<code></listPerson></code>
		<code></profileDesc></code>
		<code></particDesc></code>
		<code></fileDesc></code>
		<code></teiHeader></code>
		<code></TEI></code>

Fig. 18: Comparison of plaintext input, EzDrama markup and TEI

What is it used for?

EzDrama is used whenever a play (or a dramatic text in general) needs to be converted into a machine-readable format adhering to TEI guidelines. Some typical use-cases include:

- **Dramatic Corpora:** Projects like DraCor where large, uniformly encoded drama corpora are required.
- **Digital Humanities education:** Students who want to practice encoding. EzDrama was used several times in educational context (university classes, workshops etc).

Where you need structured data for a drama text – yet want a simpler, “friendlier” approach than writing raw TEI/XML – EzDrama provides that middle ground.

What problems does it solve?

Plain text alone often lacks the uniformity required for higher-level digital text processing, especially for drama with its structured format (acts, scenes, stage directions, speaker lines, etc.). Traditional TEI/XML encoding is powerful but can be verbose and tedious to write by hand.

By implementing a handful of text-based “metasymbols”:

- **Simplicity:** Minimal overhead compared to raw XML.
- **Consistency:** Enforces uniform patterns so that any direct speech, directions, or divisions are clearly marked.
- **Automation:** Can be processed by simple scripts, or even via user-friendly tools such as a Colab notebook or a basic web app.
- **Flexibility:** If advanced features are needed (or if partial automation is desired), you can combine EzDrama with tools like search-and-replace, regex, or GPT-based transformations.

In short, EzDrama streamlines the path from raw, inconsistent text to well-formed TEI, substantially reducing repetitive and error-prone tagging.

How can it be used? Installation, setup, requirements?

There are multiple ways to use the EzDrama parser and convert text to TEI:

Google Colab Notebook The recommended method for users with minimal technical background.

- Access the EzDrama Colab Notebook.¹³⁰
- Upload or paste your EzDrama-marked text, then run the provided cells to generate the TEI/XML.
- No local software installation required – just a Google account and a web browser.

Web App (*Alpha Version*)

- There is a basic web application available at “ezdrama.eu.pythonanywhere.com”¹³¹ (in early stages, so may break).
- Allows you to paste or upload your EzDrama text to get immediate TEI output.

Standalone Jupyter Notebook

- There is an example `ezdramaparser.ipynb` notebook that you can download and run on your local machine (requires Python and Jupyter).
- This notebook uses the same underlying `parser.py` script.

¹³⁰ https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1RNvRfTUt9ZDSbqS_nXQxzWH9L2GYr48f?usp=sharing

¹³¹ <https://ezdrama.eu.pythonanywhere.com/>

Local Usage via `parser.py`:

- For more technical users, the original Python script is available (e.g., on GitHub under `dracor-org/ezdrama`).
- Requires Python 3.x.
Clone or download the repository, open a terminal/command prompt, and run the Python script with your EzDrama file as input.

Optional: *Notepad++ Syntax Highlighting*

- If you work with Notepad++ on Windows, you can import a user-defined language configuration¹³² to color-code EzDrama markers.
- Makes editing easier and reduces markup errors.

Overall, the basic requirements are either a web browser (for Colab or the alpha web app) or a local Python environment if you prefer direct usage of the script.

Where are there difficulties? Is further development needed?

- **Unusual or Complex Formatting:** Very old or multi-column scripts with unique stage directions and uncommon textual structures may not map perfectly to the simplified EzDrama symbols. Manual adaptation might still be needed.
- **Alpha-Stage Web App:** The basic online converter may not be fully stable, and advanced features or edge cases might lead to errors.
- **Learning Curve:** Although simpler than TEI/XML, users must still learn the EzDrama markers. Some might find any markup approach intimidating.
- **Regex/Automation Limits:** Semi-automatic transformations depend on consistent text patterns. In messy or heavily stylized scripts, you'll need careful manual review to avoid mislabeling lines.
- **Further Development:**
 - Enhanced error handling (e.g., warnings for missing speaker lines).
 - Automatic bracket toggling improvements for highly nested or unconventional parentheses.
 - Enhanced XML comment and annotation support (currently commenting out is only supported for the whole lines)
 - Supporting configurable markup symbols
 - More robust user interface for the web app.
 - Testing & Continuous Integration. A set of test scripts or a test suite (e.g., using `pytest` or `unittest`) with representative EzDrama examples would help ensure that new features don't break existing functionality.

¹³² https://github.com/dracor-org/ezdrama/blob/main/Npp_ezdrama-UDL.xml

Example(s) where the tool was used

- Our CLS INFRA fellow scholar from Palacký University Olomouc encoded a dozen of Czech plays for DraCor with EasyDrama (see <https://staging.dracor.org/cze>)
- A German computational linguist of Ukrainian origin converted several plays for the Ukrainian DraCor using EasyDrama (see <https://dracor.org/u>)
- A joint seminar in 2023 by the University of Potsdam and the Freie Universität Berlin, powered by EzDrama, resulted in about 20 plays encoded for GerDraCor
- The tool was used as part of a workshop at the CLS INFRA Training School in Vienna 2024
- The tool is now used to facilitate LLM-powered encoding of plays¹³³

¹³³ Play texts usually cannot be processed by an LLM in one step, and working with chunks of EzDrama encoding is much easier than working with chunks of XML encoding with its nested hierarchical structure which is easily breakable in the process of chunking and rejoining of text.

3.5.2 “Who-is?” tool (Text: Luca Giovannini)

What is this tool?

The “Who-is-@who”¹³⁴ (short: “Who-is?”) tool has been developed by Carsten Milling to facilitate the onboarding of texts from the “Early Print Project”¹³⁵ into the EngDraCor corpus (formerly EPDraCor).¹³⁶ The tool is designed to assist researchers in correcting and updating a key component of the DraCor markup, namely the `<particDesc>` element.

The `<particDesc>` element contains a structured list of `<person>` items, each featuring an `xml:id` attribute and a `sex` attribute, which can take one of three values: “male”, “female”, or “unknown”. The `<xml:id>` element is crucial because it establishes the connection between the `<person>` items in the `<particDesc>` and the speech instances (`<sp>`) in the text, where the `xml:id` appears in the form of a `who` tag.

For example, in the following markup excerpt from Wapull’s “The Tide Tarrieth No Man” (see following code snippet)¹³⁷, the character “Help” is assigned an `xml:id` “ep000301-help”, which is then referenced in the `<sp>` element to link the speaker with their dialogue:

```

<profileDesc>
  <particDesc>
    <listPerson>
      <person xml:id="ep000301-help" sex="MALE">
        <persName>Help</persName>
      </person>
    </listPerson>
  </particDesc>
</profileDesc>

<sp who="#ep000301-help" xml:id="ep000301-e101850">
  <speaker>Helpe. </speaker>
  <l> By the masse syrs soe where he is. </l>
</sp>

```

What can it do?

The Who-is-@who tool automates and streamlines the process of assigning `who` tags to speech instances and generating the corresponding `<particDesc>`. Specifically, it allows researchers to generate a draft `<particDesc>`, easily edit the type and attribute of its items, link them to each speaker instance in the play, and download results as a JSON file.

¹³⁴ <https://dracor-org.github.io/epdracor-whois>.

¹³⁵ <https://earlyprint.org>.

¹³⁶ <https://dracor.org/eng>.

¹³⁷ <https://dracor.org/eng/wapull-the-tide-tarrieth-no-man>

What is it used for?

The tool has been primarily used for improving the quality of the markup in the EngDraCor corpus, even though it can be easily adapted to work with other corpora with similar issues.

What problems does it solve?

Since the `<particDesc>` for EngDraCor plays is generated automatically, it often contains inconsistent or incomplete data, which would spoil all following computational analyses (e.g. generation of co-occurrence networks). Common problems include variations in character names (e.g., "Duke" and "Duke of Milan"), characters with ambiguous speaker tags (e.g. numerals like "1" and "2" being used for different characters across different scenes), and automatically-generated placeholder labels (e.g., "Unassigned" or "xxx1"). By integrating automated tagging with human verification, the Who-is-@who tool enhances the accuracy and usability of computational drama corpora.

How can it be used? Installation, Setup, Requirements

The tool is web-based and does not require local installation. It can be accessed directly via EPDraCor Whols¹³⁸. The workflow is as follows:

1. Open a play in the EPDraCor Whols interface (Fig. 19).
2. Generate a draft `<particDesc>` from either:
 - The Dramatis Personae (if available in the markup).
 - The recognized speakers from speech instances `<sp>` in the text.
3. Manually refine the `<particDesc>`:
 - Remove incorrect or redundant entries.
 - Rename characters where appropriate.
 - Add missing characters and ensure correct gender classification.
4. Verify and assign who tags to speech instances:
 - Check all automatically assigned speaker tags and correct where needed.
 - If no tag is assigned and it is not possible to readily determine the correct combination, it is possible to inspect the Early Print version of the play to determine the speaker. It can be accessed via the direct link next to the plays' name in the page header.
5. Download the cleaned metadata in JSON format. The JSON file will need to be placed in the meta/speakers folder in the EngDraCor Github repository,¹³⁹ from where it will be taken up during the automatic corpus deployment.

¹³⁸ <https://dracor-org.github.io/epdracor-whois/plays>

¹³⁹ <https://github.com/dracor-org/engdracor/tree/main/meta/speakers>.

Where are the challenges? What further development is needed?

While the Who-is-@who tool is highly effective, its prototypical character means the interface is not always stable. Furthermore, progress cannot be saved, so the refinement of a play (including downloading the output JSON) must be completed in one session. Future developments might involve the integration of more advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) routines for <particDesc> generation and automatic disambiguation.

Example use cases

The Who-is-@who tool has been successfully applied for cleaning more than 400 early modern English plays, which constitute the bulk of EngDraCor. By automating metadata generation while allowing for manual refinement, the Who-is-@who tool significantly improves the quality of digital drama corpora and facilitates computational literary research.

Who is @who in EPDraCor				
Authors	Title	ID	DP	@who
A., R.	The Valiant Welshman	A05801	yes	
Alexander, William	Caesar	A16527_04	yes	@who
Alexander, William	Croesus	A16527_01	yes	@who
Alexander, William	Darius	A16527_02	yes	@who
Alexander, William	The Alexandraean Tragedy	A16527_03	yes	@who
Amerie, Robert · Davies, Richard	Chester's Triumph	A18589	no	@who
Anon.	1 Jeronimo, with the Wars of Portugal	A04941	no	@who
Anon.	A Knack to Know a Knave	A04888	no	@who
Anon.	A Larum for London, or The Siege of Antwerp	A06270	no	@who
Anon.	Alphonsus, Emperor of Germany	A31675	yes	@who
Anon.	Arden of Faversham	A20951	no	@who
Anon.	Band, Cuff, and Ruff, or Exchange Ware at the Second Hand	A03424	no	@who
Anon.	Bonduca, or The British Heroine	A27180	yes	
Anon.	Caesar and Pompey, or Caesar's Revenge	A73627	yes	@who
Anon.	Canterbury His Change of Diet	A52953	no	@who
Anon.	Emilia	A39384	yes	
Anon.	Encyclochoria, or Universal Motion	A38208	no	
Anon.	Fair Em	A21328	no	@who
Anon.	Henry II, King of England, with the Death of Rosamond	A30781	yes	
Anon.	Jack Straw	A13062	no	@who
Anon.	Knavery in All Trades, or The Coffee-House	A63181	yes	
Anon.	Nero	A08065	no	@who

Fig. 19. Tool interface - play selection menu

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Who is @who in EPDraCor
↓

Alexander, William: Caesar [A16527_04](#) ×

<p>Dramatis Personae ☰</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IVNO. CAESAR. ANTONIVS. CICERO. DECIVS BRVTVS. CAIVS CASSIVS. MARCVS BRVTVS. PORTIA. CALPHVRNIA. NVNTIVS. 	<p>particDesc</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <table border="0" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;">Name</td> <td style="width: 50%; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;">ID</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2" style="text-align: center; padding-top: 5px;"> <input type="button" value="ADD"/> </td> </tr> </table> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; margin-bottom: 5px; text-align: center; color: #0070C0;"> NEW FROM DRAMATIS PERSONAE </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; text-align: center; color: #0070C0;"> NEW FROM EXISTING @WHO ATTRIBUTES </div>	Name	ID	<input type="button" value="ADD"/>		<p>Speakers</p> <table border="0" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr><td>luno .</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Ant.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Caesar .</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Anto.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Caesar</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Caes.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>An.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Caes</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Dec.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Ci.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Cic.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Marc. Brut.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Ca Cass.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> <tr><td>Brut.</td><td><input type="text"/></td><td>▼</td><td>▼</td></tr> </table>	luno .	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Ant.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Caesar .	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Anto.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Caesar	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Caes.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	An.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Caes	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Dec.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Ci.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Cic.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Marc. Brut.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Ca Cass.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼	Brut.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼
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Marc. Brut.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼																																																											
Ca Cass.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼																																																											
Brut.	<input type="text"/>	▼	▼																																																											

Fig. 20 Tool interfaces – play editing menu

3.6 Connecting to External Services

We have introduced a new feature to the DraCor frontend called the “Tool Tab”. This tab provides convenient links to third-party tools, enhancing the usability and integration capabilities of the platform. The Tool Tab offers quick access to various third-party tools that can be used to analyze or process texts from DraCor corpora. Users can select the desired serialization format for the text or subset of text they wish to analyze, with options including Full Text (TEI-encoded), Plain Text, Spoken Text, and Stage Directions. At the moment it is only possible to load data of a single play, not a whole corpus.

Most third-party tools support loading data from an external location. The URL of the source can be specified in a parameter: “Voyant Tools” supports a query parameter `input`, “Gephi Lite” supports a query parameter `file`, and the “CLARIN Language Switchboard” includes the URL as part of the path. The Tool Tab automatically includes the respective URL to the DraCor API endpoint in the link to the respective tool. This addition to the DraCor frontend streamlines the process of using external tools with DraCor data, making it easier for researchers to leverage different analysis and processing capabilities without manual URL configuration.

The screenshot shows the DraCor frontend interface for the play "Emilia Galotti" by Gotthold Ephraim Lessing. The page has a dark blue header with navigation links: ABOUT, CORPORA, TOOLS, HOW TO, and MERCH. The main content area features the play title "Emilia Galotti" and the author's name "Gotthold Ephraim Lessing". Below the title, there are options for text layer analysis: "Full text (TEI-encoded)" (selected), "Spoken text", and "Stage directions". A list of external tools is provided, including "Voyant Tools" and "CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard". A tooltip on the right explains that the selected text layer will be loaded from the DraCor API for external analysis.

Fig. 21 “Tool tab” in the DraCor front end for the play “Emilia Galotti” by Gotthold Ephraim Lessing, <https://dracor.org/ger/lessing-emilia-galotti#tools>

3.6.1 Voyant Tools

The open source Voyant Tools project (<https://voyant-tools.org>), developed by Stéfan Sinclair and Geoffrey Rockwell since 2016, is “a web-based text reading and analysis environment”, “designed to facilitate reading and interpretive practices for digital humanities students and scholars as well as for the general public”.¹⁴⁰ It can be used particularly well in the classroom. The connection with Voyant makes it easier to get started with the quantitative analysis of DraCor plays.

Fig. 22: “Emilia Galotti”, imported into Voyant via DraCor

3.6.2 CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard

The CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard (<https://switchboard.clarin.eu>) is an environment that “helps you to find and start tools that can process your research data”.¹⁴¹ In particular, it offers an easy-to-use option for transferring your own data to tools for various natural language processing tasks (such as lemmatization, named entity recognition, part-of-speech tagging or

¹⁴⁰ <https://voyant-tools.org/docs/tutorial-about.html>

¹⁴¹ <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/help#faq>

dependency parsing). The connection of DraCor with the Switchboard opens up the analysis of DraCor data for more advanced forms of computational linguistics.

Fig. 23 “Emilia Galotti”, handed over to the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard via DraCor

3.6.3 Gephi Lite

Gephi Lite (<https://gephi.org/gephi-lite/>) is a light-weight web-based version of the Gephi software, which can be used to easily “visualize and explore networks and graphs”.¹⁴² While DraCor itself focuses on the analysis and visualisation of networks, the connection to Gephi lite enables a comparative perspective on the character networks in the plays.

¹⁴² <https://github.com/gephi/gephi-lite#readme>

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Fig. 24 "Emilia Galotti", handed over to Gephi Lite via DraCor

4. Key achievements of WP 7

Over the course of the four-year CLS INFRA project, WP7: „Building the Ecosystem of and for Programmable Corpora“ turned the concept of “Programmable Corpora” into a concrete infrastructure. At the core is the drama platform „DraCor“, now a multi-component showcase that demonstrates how literary data, services, and tools can grow together into an open, versioned and research-driven ecosystem.

Overall, the following key achievements can be summarized:

- **Discussed and contextualized the concept of “Programmable Corpora”** – corpora that provide their texts, metadata and derivatives through documented, machine-actionable APIs, inspired by Aaron Swartz’s vision of a “programmable web”;
- **Delivered a fully-working prototype** – DraCor, with more than 20 corpora and around 4 000 plays, in homogeneous TEI/XML, versioned by Git, accessible via API endpoints and with a web front-end for corpus browsing, one-click downloads and visualisations;
- **Released DraCor API 1.0** – added explicit versioning in every path, harmonised names, removed deprecated endpoints, embedded response schemas and published full OpenAPI docs and an ODD/ontology for data features;
- **Implemented the Distributed Text Services (DTS) standard** – based on the DTS specification, we introduced four new endpoints enabling among other things fine-grained, citable access to the texts in the DraCor corpora;
- **Made the “Programmable Corpora” architecture transferable** – in a series of experiments, we e.g. „swaggerised“ the Folger Shakespeare API or re-used the DraCor front-end for POSTDATA poetry, proving that our approach can be transferred to other sets of literary data;
- **Stabilised “living corpora” for reproducible research** – we introduced a way to cite “living corpora” using Git commits and containerised complete research stacks with “StableDraCor” for full reproducibility;
- **Added new tools to the DraCor ecosystems and connected DraCor to external tools** – with *EzDrama* and *Who-is?* we introduced two helper tools for the TEI encoding of new plays for DraCor; with the DraCor ToolTab we implemented opportunities for easily analyzing DraCor plays with Voyant Tools, CLARIN Switchboard and Gephi Lite;
- **Open Science and community engagement** – DraCor relies on open licences and open GitHub workflows; in the period of the CLS INFRA project (2021 to 2025), a total of 84 scholarly publications were published¹⁴³ on the basis of the open DraCor data and the DraCor ecosystem.

¹⁴³ Cf. <https://dracor.org/doc/research>

5. Future Work

We are currently focusing our plans for future projects on five areas of activity, which we will briefly outline here:

- First, we are continuing to work on the transferability of the DraCor infrastructure to other application scenarios in the context of computational literary studies. Here we are currently examining the development of a programmable corpora instance for ELTeC, the “European Literary Text Collection”.¹⁴⁴ In this context, we are also continuing our work on the “DraCor React Component Library”.¹⁴⁵
- Second, we want to intensify our work on knowledge extraction from the DraCor (meta)data and set up a DraCor Knowledge Graph.
- Third, we are experimenting with large language models and, thanks to the exchange with Stijn Meijers from Wolk,¹⁴⁶ have recently set up a prototype for a natural language API layer using a Model Context Protocol Server (MCP)¹⁴⁷.
- Fourth, we are working on a new strategy for the provision of training materials as Open Educational Resources, based on the Jupyter Book software. The publication of a DraCor textbook is planned for late 2025 or early 2026.
- Finally, we are planning a major community event, the DraCor Summit in September 2025.¹⁴⁸

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.distant-reading.net/eltec/>

¹⁴⁵ <https://dracor-org.github.io/dracor-react/?path=/>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.wolk.work>

¹⁴⁷ <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-mcp>

¹⁴⁸ <https://summit.dracor.org/>

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